

**“INVESTIGATIONS OF PHYTO-
CONSTITUENTS FROM SOME ETHNO-
MEDICINAL PLANTS WITH REFERENCE TO
SECONDARY METABOLITES”**

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DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN BOTANY

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MAY. 2018

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**Investigations of Phyto-constituents from some ethno-medicinal plants with reference to secondary metabolites**” submitted to the Faculty of Science, **North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon** in fulfillment of the requirements for the award of degree for **Doctor of Philosophy in BOTANY**, embodies the original research work carried out by **Mr. Pathan Amanulla Khan** under my supervision and has not been submitted in part or full for any other degree or diploma of this or any other university.

It is further certified that the scholar fulfills all the requirements as laid down by the University for the purpose of submission of Ph.D. thesis.

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DECLARATION

I, **Mr. Pathan Amanulla Khan** hereby declare that this thesis entitled “**Investigations of Phyto-constituents from some ethno-medicinal plants with reference to secondary metabolites**” submitted to the **North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon** for the award of degree of **Doctor of Philosophy in Botany**, is the result of bonafide research work carried out by me under the guidance of **Dr. Madhukar B. Patil**, Associate professor in Department of Botany, J. E. S s Arts, Commerce & Science College, Dist. Nandurbar. I further declare that this thesis or any part of it has not been submitted forward of any other degree/diploma of this or any other University.

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*"The woods are lovely dark and deep, But I have promises to keep,
and miles to go before I sleep, and miles to go before I sleep"*

--'Richard Frost'

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ABBREVIATIONS

% = Per cent / Percentage

AD = Anno Domini

AICRP = All India Coordinate Research Project

AOAC = Association of Official Analytical Chemists

BC = Before Christ

BS = *Boswellia serrata* Roxb.

BSI = Botanical Survey of India

BSL = *Boswellia serrata* Leaves

Br = Bark

cm = centimeter

CS = *Caturnarenagam spinosa* (thunb.) Tirven.

CSL = *Caturnarenagam spinosa* Leaves

E. coli = *Escherichia coli*

Fig. = Figure

FTIR = Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

g/mol = Gram per mol

GC = Gas chromatography

GC-MS = Gas chromatography and mass spectrometry

gm = Gram (s)

HB = *Hardwickia binata* Roxb.

HBL = *Hardwickia binata* Leaves

HPLC = High Performance Liquid Chromatography

HPTLC = High Pressure Thin layered Chromatography

hr = Hours

IP = *Ischaemum pilosum* (Willd.) Wight.)

IPL = *Ischaemum pilosum* Leaves

IR = Infra red

LC-MS = Liquid chromatography Mass spectrophotometry

MIC = Minimum Inhibitory Concentration

mm = millimeters

MTCC = Microbial Type Culture Collection

MW = Molecular weight

NIST = National Institute of Standards and Technology

nm = nanometer

°C = Degree Celsius (Temperature)

RAPD = Randomly Amplified polymorphic DNA

R_f = Retention factor

RT = Retention time

St = Stem

TLC = Thin layer chromatographic

UV = Ultraviolet

UV-Vis = Ultraviolet visible

v/v = Volume by volume

w/v = Weight by volume

WHO = World Health Organization

μl = Micro liter

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Chapter 5.

Conclusion

CHAPTER 5**CONCLUSIONS**

Phytochemical study of some Ethnomedicinal plant with many parameters and literature reviewed conclude that, the current reported work has further tremendous scope and demands in medicinal based industries. The complete summarized research work is reported different sections as per the systematic protocols and experiments as follows.

The current work is proposed with objectives like the study of folk medicinal properties, plant part uses, systematic enumerations, proximate analysis, primary phytochemicals study, and various chromatography experiments based of phytochemical study. All these work has been designed for four wild plant, those are not much utilized for mankind in daily life but abundantly occur in local forest, that are listed below.

- i. *Boswellia serrata* Roxb. Family: Burseraceae
- ii. *Catunaregam spinosa* (Thunb.) Tirven.: Family: Rubiaceae
- iii. *Hardwickia binata* Roxb.: Family: Caesalpiniaceae
- iv. *Ischaemum pilosum* (Klein.ex Willd.) Wt., Family: Poaceae

Collection, identification and nomenclature of these plants had been done with local flora and different parts are used for experiment purpose. All above four plants has been collected from Toranmal forest area, Shahada Dist Nandurbar. Extraction techniques and different solvent system had been used by soxhlet apparatus and related methods on collected dry plant parts. The extracted plant part material in different solvent were filtered and stored in cold temp for farther use. With the help of all standard protocols and methods, lab work had been done for all experiments and good results were recorded in various parameters.

Results of Ethnomedicinal properties were listed for each plant and their parts as per recorded from tribal's and available literature. All collected plant were systematically studied and reported with the help of Flora Dhule and Nandurbar District by D A Patil and Flora of Maharashtra.

With the help of Association of Official Analytical Chemists 1990 guidelines, all plants samples were tested for proximate analysis recorded results for Moisture content, dry matter content and Ash content were recorded. It was found that cumulative results for total moisture content for *Boswellia serrata* Roxb, *Catunaregam spinosa*, *Hardwickia binata* Roxb and *Ischaemum pilosum* (Willd.) are 59.66%, 64.33%, 57.16% and 52.16% respectively. Were total dry matters content for *Boswellia serrata* Roxb, *Catunaregam spinosa*, *Hardwickia binata* Roxb and *Ischaemum pilosum* (Willd.) are 40.33%, 35.66%, 43.16% and 47.33% respectively and total ash content for *Boswellia serrata* Roxb, *Catunaregam spinosa*, *Hardwickia binata* Roxb and *Ischaemum pilosum* (Willd.) are 14.33%, 16.50%, 36.50% and 30.33% respectively.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis for leaves, Stem and Root bark were done in all four plant among 12 different parameters like Alkaloids, Anthraquinone, Cardiac glycosides, Coumarins, Flavonoids, Glycosides, Phenols, Reducing sugars, Saponins, Steroids, Tannin and Triterpenes in different six solvent system and recorded significant results in all four plant. That's confirming the medicinal properties of plants (Cox, P. 1990 and, Aftab and Said 1999)

Alkaloids, which are reported to have dramatic physiological activities and act mainly on controlling nervous system, were screened, **Carotenoids** having nutritional importance as vitamin A (Cox, P. and Balick, M 1994) were also observed in preliminary phytochemical tests. **Coumarins**, reported to have anticoagulation, estrogenic, vasodilation, antibacterial and antihelmintic properties were found (Cox, P. 1990). **Flavonoids** having antiviral, anti-inflammatory and cytotoxic activities and used in the treatment of capillary fragility, hypertension, diabetic retinopathy, rheumatic fever and arthritis (Raghavaiah, V 1962) were observed. **Saponins**, well known for their

expectorant, spasmolytic and antitissue activities (Raghavaiah, V 1962) were observed. Steroids and Triterpenoids, which are known for antiinflammatory, lipolytic and anti-cholesteremic activities (Inglis, T.J.J 1996), were recorded. Gallic tannins, which are well documented for the astringent, cytotoxic and antineoplastic activities and used in diarrhoea, haemorrhage, wounds healing and deep burns were observed (Bannister *et al.*, 2000).

Thin layer chromatographic result has been recorded for all four plants leaves extract and Rf value were shown presence of probable compounds in mobile phase like Chloroform: Methanol (5:1) shows presence of Alkaloids and Glycosides, Methanol: Hexane (3:1), shows Flavonoids and Saponins and Ethanol: Acetone (3:2.1) shows presence of Terpenoids in *Boswellia serrata*. Were in same result is observed in leaves of *Catunaregam spinosa*, *Hardwickia binata* and *Ischaemum pilosum* respectively.

In the present study of TLC showed the presence of bioactive compound such as alkaloids, Glycosides, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, etc. This study also leads to the further research in the way of isolation and identification of the active compound from the leaf, stem and root of all four plant using chromatographic and spectroscopic techniques, similar results also observed in *Centella asiatica* L. by Sanjay *et al.*, 2013.

UV-VIS spectrophotometer analysis the extracts were scanned in the wavelength ranging from 200-1100 nm and the characteristic peaks were detected. The peak values of the UV-VIS were recorded in Ethanol Extract (60% Conc.) and Chloroform Extract (60% Conc.) for leaves, Stem bark and Root bark in different 22 UV spectral tests for all four plant. In the range of 600 nm to 700 nm significant peaks were observed.

For *Boswellia serrata* UV-VIS spectrophotometer shows two peaks in Leaves sample on 450 nm and 675 nm. In Stem bark extract also recorded on 450 nm and 670 nm in screening. Only single sharp peak was recorded at 650 in Root bark in ethanol extract, were in chloroform extract leaves samples shows sharp and deep peak at 400 nm

and 675 nm. For Stem bark extract small peaks on 420 nm and 670 nm were recorded. Single peak was recorded at 675 nm in Root bark.

For *Catunaregam spinosa* UV-VIS spectrophotometer shows, Stem bark extract no clear peak in range between 400-600 nm were at 670 nm a narrow peak in screening. In Root bark decline graph been recorded from 300 nm to onwards indicated not any components under screening of ethanol extract were in chloroform leaves samples shows two sharp but small peak in range between 500-600 nm and one sharp large peak at 675 nm. For Stem bark extract 675 nm were recorded and 650 nm peaks screened in Root bark.

In UV-VIS spectrophotometer result for *Hardwickia binata* In ethanol shows decline graph with no remarkable peak in Leaves sample within 300-450 nm range. In Stem bark and Root bark extract same was recorded within 300-400 nm and 300-450 nm respectively were in chloroform extract leaves samples shows sharp and deep peak at 675 nm. For Stem bark extract short peak at 670 nm recorded. Single peak was recorded at 670 nm in Root bark.

In UV-VIS spectrophotometer result of *Ischaemum pilosum* a peak in Leaves sample in 600-700 nm range and in root extract irregular peaks in 300-400 nm ranges in ethanol extract were in Chloroform extract leaves samples shows a sharp a peak in range 450 nm and irregular peaks within 300-400 nm.

An FTIR result signifies clearly that identical functional groups and nuclear structure is present in the plant extract of various solvents. for the Leaves extract in acetone solvent shows characteristic absorption bands for Amines (N-H) at 3374,87 cm⁻¹, Carboxylic acids (O-H) at 2917,75 cm⁻¹, Aldehydes, (C=O) at 1703,81 cm⁻¹, Aromatic Rings (C=C) at 1612,87 cm⁻¹, Nitro Compounds (NO₂) at 1448,89 cm⁻¹, Alkanes (C-H) at 1357,84 cm⁻¹, Alcohols (C-O) at 1206,78 cm⁻¹, Esters (C-O) at 1072,85 cm⁻¹ and Alkenes (C-H) at 874,98 cm⁻¹ like compounds in starch between 4000 to 650 cm⁻¹ in

Boswellia serrata similar results were recorded in other plants shows presence of functional groups of phytochemical.

In FTIR result of *Catunaregam spinosa* was recorded that Leaves extract in acetone solvent shows characteristic absorption bands for Carboxylic acids (O-H) at 2920,97 cm⁻¹, Aldehydes and Ketones, (C=O) at 1735,95 cm⁻¹, Aromatic Rings (C=C) at 1459,98 cm⁻¹ and Esters (C-O) at 1165,97 cm⁻¹ compounds in starch between 4000 to 650 cm⁻¹ in spectral search.

For *Hardwickia binata* FTIR results for the Leaves extract in acetone solvent shows characteristic absorption bands for Amines (N-H) at 3383,96 cm⁻¹, Carboxylic acids (O-H) at 2850,97 cm⁻¹, Ketones (C=O) at 1734,96 cm⁻¹, Aromatic Rings (C=C) at 1451,97 cm⁻¹ and Esters (C-O) at 1166,97 cm⁻¹ peak value these compounds are found between 4000 to 650 cm⁻¹ in spectral search

Were for the *Ischaemum pilosum* FTIR results for the Leaves extract in acetone solvent shows characteristic absorption bands for Carboxylic acids (O-H) at 2956,92 cm⁻¹, Alkanes (O-H) at 2849,89 cm⁻¹, Aldehydes (C=O) at 1735,92 cm⁻¹, Aromatic Rings (C=C) at 1462,95 cm⁻¹, Alkanes (C-H) at 1377,97 cm⁻¹, Esters (C-O) 1166,95 cm⁻¹ and Phenyl Ring (C-H) 758,97 cm⁻¹ peak value these compounds are found between 4000 to 650 cm⁻¹ in spectral search. The infrared functional group characteristics were also cited similar in literature (John 2000, Kashem and Rabiul 2006, Meenakshi *at el.*, 2009 Naira and Karvekar 2010)

The presence of an important component can be resolved by **GC-MS analysis** and their biological activities. Thus this type of GC-MS analysis is the first step towards understanding the nature of active principles in this medicinal plant and this type of study will helpful for further detailed study. GC MS results and data were recorded for all four plants for their leaves and were indentified with National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and on Dr. Duke's Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical Databases by Dr. Jim Duke of the Agricultural Research. It was found that various phytochemicals

including those compounds which bear therapeutic activity and properties are reported in these current experimental plants. Around 34 different chemical compounds, with their name, molecular formula and structures were listed as per GC MS data retention time (RT) probability of compounds and library search as well as with their properties in Chapter 4.

Among all above listed phyto constitutes are with large diversity and distributed in **Alkaloids** like, 2-Methylpyridine 2,4-dimethylpyridine, 4-Piperidinone, 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-, 8-methylquinoline, 1H Pyrrole-2,5-dione, 3-ethyl-4- methyl- and many more. Alkaloids present special interest because of their pharmacological activities. Many reports revealed the presence of alkaloids in marine algae and some of them were investigated for their biological activity (Güven *et al.*, 2010).

Were some **Phenolics** compounds like 4-Ethenyl-2-methoxyphenol, Phenol, 3-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-methoxy-, Phenol, 2,6-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4- methyl, Phenol, 2,2-methylenebis[6-(1,1- dimethylethyl)-4-methyl- were recorded. Phenolic compounds were reported to have many pharmacological properties (e.g. anticarcinogenic and antimicrobial activities and effects against neurodegenerative pathologies) (Esposito *et al.*, 2002; Oueslatia *et al.*, 2012).

Components like **Terpenes** are 3-Buten-2-one, 4-(2,2,6-trimethyl-7-oxabicyclo [4.1.0] hept-1-yl)- , (7aR)-5,6,7,7a-Tetrahydro-4,4,7a-trimethyl 2(4H)-benzofuranone, 2,6,10,14-Tetramethylpentadecane, (–)-Loliolide, Neophytadiene, 2,6,10,14 Tetramethylhexadecane, (2E,7R,11R)-3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-2- hexadecen-1-ol, 4,8,12,16-Tetramethyl-heptadecan-4-olide, etc are observed. Terpenes like Neophytadiene and phytol were the dominant terpenes and represented 149.8 and 208.17 mg/100 g dry biomass. Neophytadiene and phytol were detected in several plants and some microalgae (Jeng and Huh, 2004; Venkata *et al.*, 2012). Neophytadiene was identified as strong bactericidal, antifungal, antipyretic, analgesic, antioxidant and vermifugic (Venkata *et al.*, 2012), while, phytol that is used in the fragrance industry, cosmetics, shampoos, toilet soaps, household cleaners, and detergents showed

antimicrobial, anticancer, antidiuretic activity and was found to be a precursor of vitamin E and vitamin K (Daines *et al.*, 2003 and Netscher, 2007; McGinty *et al.*, 2010).

Steroids like Cholestan-3-ol, (3b,5b)-, Cholest-5-en-3-ol, (3b)-, Cholestanol, Ergost-5-en-3-ol, (3b,24R)-, Stigmasta-5,22-dien-3-b-ol, c-Sitosterol, Stigmastan-3,5-diene, etc was recorded in different plants from GCMS data. Sterols and some of their derivatives were previously found to have played an important role in lowering LDL cholesterol levels in vivo (Francavilla *et al.*, 2010). With all above secondary metabolites also various forms of Ketones, Fatty acids, Fatty alcohols, Esters and Hydrocarbons were found as per GC MS data retention time (RT) probability of compounds and library search.

Anti bacterial and anti fungal activity of all four experimental plants were done by four different bacterial strain and two fungal strain in five different solvents system and zone of inhibition were recorded after 72 hr. over all it shows that their methanol and ethanol act as good solvent system for antimicrobial work and significant anti microbial activity were found in all four plant extract in each type of extracts against fungal and bacterial stain.

Specifically the best microbial controlled by leaf methanol extract of *B. serrata* that control fungus *Candida albicans* (11 ± 0.4 mm) were Methanol leaf extract of *C. spinosa* best control bacterial growth for *Escherichia coli* (10 ± 0.4 mm). on other hands Pet ether leaf extract of *H. binata* best control bacterial growth for *Staphylococcus aureus* (22 ± 0.2 mm) and Pet ether leaf extract of *I. pilosum* best control bacterial growth for *Staphylococcus aureus* (12 ± 0.8 mm).

Recommendations

Today, there is more and more interest in drugs derived from plants. This interest comes mainly from the belief that plant based medicine is safe and reliable, compared to expensive synthetic drugs that have adverse effects. To determine the potential and promote the use of herbal medicine, it is essential to intensify the study of medicinal plants that find their place in folklore. Therefore, these plants should be studied to better understand their properties, safety and efficacy. This study was conducted to make a path and develop new leads for better and safer therapeutic agents. Further studies are needed to identify the pure component and establish a precise mechanism of action of plant extracts. Since the plants were safe in animal models, they can be studied for clinical trials and may be recommended for the use of poly-herbal formulations.

Additional efforts at the molecular level should be made to establish the exact mechanism of action of all therapeutic actions of plant extracts and isolated compounds. In comparison with established standard drugs used in studies, these lead molecules can be taken for further improvement.

Finally, for the development of a better therapeutic agent for clinical evaluation, detailed pharmacology and toxicology including genotoxicity and reproductive toxicology studies must be performed in order to generate data with huge potential as well as affirmed pharmacological actions. The discovery and application of these natural drugs will play a role in human and veterinary medicine in the future. Additional effort at molecular level should be carried out to establish the exact mechanism of action for all therapeutic actions of the plant extracts and its isolates. The discovery and application of such natural drugs will play a role in the future.

Areas of further research

The following studies can be made in this area of research further,

- Production of phyto constitution by *in- vitro* for better production.
- Testing of medicinal properties and their mode of action on specific animal models.
- High throughput screening of individual phyto-compounds among all studied plants.
- Real time PCR analysis on microchip for authentication of plant materials and their genetic relatedness from plant samples of different geographical areas.
- Multi-component phytochemical analysis, clinically relevant and micro array based.
- Proteomic and Metabolism based tests for plant extracts.
- Study and enhancement of biosynthesis pathway for therapeutically active compounds.

Chapter 6.

6. References

- ✓ Aarts T (1998). The dietary supplements industry: A Market Analysis. Dietary Supplements conference, Nutritional Business International.
- ✓ Adebajo AO, Adewumi CO, Essein EE (1983). Anti-infective agent of higher plants. International Symposium of Medicinal Plants. 5 th Edition, University of Ife, Nigeria, pp. 152-158.
- ✓ Afolayan AJ and AOT Ashafa (2009). Chemical composition and antimicrobial activity of the essential oil from *Chrysocoma ciliata* L. leaves. J. Med. Plants Res. 3: 390-394.
- ✓ Afolayan AJ, JJM Meyer (1997). Antimicrobial activity of 3, 5, 7- trihydroxyflavone isolated from the shoot of *Helichrisum aureonitens*. J. Ethnopharmacol 57: 177- 181.
- ✓ Afsar, N.; Siddiqui, G.; Ayub, Z (2012). Imposax detection in *Babylonia spirata* (Gastropoda: Buccinidae) from Pakistan (Northern Arabian Sea). Indian J. Geo-Mar. Sci., v. 41, n. 5, p. 418-424
- ✓ Aftab, K. and Said, A.H (1999). Phytomedicine new and old approach. *Hemdard Medicus*. 42(2), 11-15.
- ✓ Agarry OO, Olaleye MT, Bello-Micheal CO (2005). Comparative antimicrobial activities of *Aloe vera* gel and Leaf. Afr. J. Biotechnol., 04(12): 1413-1414.
- ✓ Agrawal S.S., Singh V.K. (1999). Immuno modulators-A review of studies on Indian medicinal plants and synthetic peptides, Part- 1, Medicinal plants, Proc. Indian Natl Sci Acad. ; 65: 179-204.
- ✓ Agrios, G.N (1997). Plant diseases caused by prokaryotes: bacteria and mollicutes. Plant pathology. Academic press, San Diego, USA.
- ✓ Ahangarpour A, heidari H, Fatemeh R A, Pakmehr M, Shanbazian H, Ahmadil, Mombeiniz and Mehrangin B H (2014). Supplementations on blood lipids, hepatic enzymes and fructosamine level in type 2 diabetic patients. *Phytopharm* Vol. 15 No. 3 PP 31-32

- ✓ Ahmed Al-Harrasi and Salim Al-Saidi (2003). Phytochemical Analysis of the Essential Oil from Botanically Certified Oleogum Resin of *Boswellia sacra* (Omani Luban). *Molecules* 2008, 13, 2181-2189; DOI: 10.3390/molecules13092181
- ✓ Akunyili, D. N. (2003). The role of regulation of medicinal plants and phytomedicine in socio- economic development, AGM/SC of the Nigerian Society of Pharmacognosy, 1- 7.
- ✓ *All India coordinate research project (AICRP-2016) on weed management (28th annual report) 2016*. Dr. PDKV, akola (M.S.)
- ✓ Alok Prakash and Suneetha V. (2014). *Punica granatum* (Pomegranate) Rind Extract as a Potent Substitute for L Ascorbic Acid With respect To the Antioxidant Activity. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 5(2) PP- 597-603
- ✓ Alok Sharma, C. Shanker, Lalit Kumar Tyagi, Mahendra Singh and Ch.V.Rao (2008). Herbal Medicine for Market Potential in India: An Overview. *Academic Journal of Plant Sciences* 1 (2): 26-36,
- ✓ Ambujakshi, H.R., Thakkar, H. and Shyamnanda (2009). Anthelmintic activity of *Gmelina arborea* Roxb. Leaves extract. *Ind. J. of Res. Dev.* 1(9, (1-4).
- ✓ American Cancer Society (2000) Guidelines for Cancer Detection.
- ✓ Ammar Altemimi, Naoufal Lakhssassi, Azam Baharlouei, Dennis G. Watson and David A. Lightfoot (2017). Review Phytochemicals: Extraction, Isolation, and Identification of Bioactive Compounds from Plant Extracts. *Plants*. , 6, 42; pp-1-23
- ✓ Ammirato, P.V. (1987). Organization events during somatic embryogenesis. In: *Plant tissue and cell culture*. C.E. Green, D.A. Somers, W.P. Hackett and D.D.Biesboer (eds). Pp 57-81. Alan R Liss, Inc.,New York.
- ✓ Anil Kumar (2012). Ethnobotanical investigation of some plant used by tribals of Bori Wild life Sanctuary in Hoshangabad district M P. *Ethnobotany*. Vol. 24, PP. 123-125
- ✓ Anitha Sri S (2016). Pharmacological Activity of *Vinca* Alkaloids. *Research & Reviews: Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. Vol 4 Issue 3 PP-27-34

- ✓ Anon (1998). Wealth of India: A Dictionary of Indian Raw Materials and Industrial Products, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, vol. 5, pp. 6–8.
- ✓ Anonymous (1997). Conservation Assessment and Management Plan Workshop Process. WWF, India.
- ✓ Anonymous (2001). Appendix I, II and III to Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora. Arlington VA: US Fish & Wildlife Services:32 pp.
- ✓ Ansari A and Khan LH (1981). Chemical analysis of fruit of the *Randia dumetorum* of Bhupal Area. J. Sci Res (Bhupal): Vol (2);133-4.
- ✓ Antony Sandosh T, M. Paul John Peter and J. Yesu Raj. Phytochemical Analysis of *Stylosanthes fruticosa* using UV-VIS, FTIR and GC-MS. *Research Journal of Chemical Sciences*. Vol. 3(11), 14-23, November (2013)
- ✓ Arash, R., Koshy, P. and Sekaran, M. (2010) Antioxidant Potential and Phenol Content of Ethanol Extract of Selected Malaysian Plants. *Research Journal of Biotechnology*, 5, 16-19.
- ✓ Arias, T.D., (1999). Glossaries de Medicaments: desarrollo, evaluation use. Washington: Organization Pan-American de La Salud. Organization Mundial de La Salud, p. 171.
- ✓ Arlene P. Bartolome, Irene M. Villaseñor and Wen-Chin Yang. (2013). *Bidens pilosa* L. (Asteraceae): Botanical Properties, Traditional Uses, Phytochemistry, and Pharmacology. Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine. Volume 2013, Article ID 340215, PP-1-51
- ✓ Arshiya Sultana, Khaleeq Ur Rahman, AR. Padmaja, Shafeeq Ur Rahman (2013). *Boswellia serrata* Roxb. A Traditional Herb with Versatile Pharmacological Activity: A Review. *IJPSR*. 4(6): 2106-2117.
- ✓ Arunabha Mallik, Damodhar Goupalea , Hemant Dhongadeb and Satish Nayaka (2012) Evaluation of *Boswellia Serrata* oleo-gum resin for wound healing activity. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*, 2 (2): 457-463

- ✓ Arvind Kumar Shakya (2016). Medicinal plants: Future source of new drugs. *International Journal of Herbal Medicine*. 4(4): 59-64
- ✓ Ashraful Alam M, M. Rowshanul Habib, Farjana Nikkon, Matiar Rahman and M. Rezaul Karim (2008). Antimicrobial Activity of Akanda (*Calotropis gigantea* L.) on Some Pathogenic Bacteria. *Bangladesh J. Sci. Ind. Res.* 43(3), 397-404,
- ✓ Asok K. J., Vijay V. W. and Chitralaelcha K. (2011). “Conservation status of some miniature sacred groves in Jhabua District (M. P.)”. *Ethnobotany*, Vol. 23, PP.106-115
- ✓ Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC). *Official Methods of Analysis*, 15th ed.; AOAC: Arlington, VA, USA, 1990.
- ✓ Ateb DA, Erdo UOT (2003). Antimicrobial activities of various medicinal and commercial plant extracts. *Turk. J. Biol.*, 27: 157-162.
- ✓ Atta-ur-Rahman and M. I. Choudhary (1995). Diterpenoid and Steroidal Alkaloids, , *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 12, 361-379.
- ✓ Atta-ur-Rahman, M. I. Choudhary, F. Asif, A. Farooq, M. Yaqoob (1998). Quettamine- type Alkaloids from *Leontice leontopetalum*. *Nat. Prod. Lett.* 12, 255 – 261.
- ✓ Awe IS, Sodipo OA (2001). Purification of saponins of root of *Blighia sapida* Koenlg-Holl. *Nigerian Journal of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*. 16 (37), 201-204
- ✓ Baker JT, Borris RP, Carte B, Cordell GA, Soejarto DD, Cragg GM, Gupta MP, Iwu MM, Madulid DR, Tyler VE (1995). Natural product drug discovery and development: New perspective on international collaboration. *J. Nat. Prod.* 58: 1325-1357.
- ✓ Balachandran, N., Rajendiran K. & Gastmans, W. (2014). Biogeographical Constraint Of Some Indo-Sri Lankan Species From The Tropical Dry Evergreen Forest f Tamil Nadu, India. *I.J.S.N.*, Vol.5 (3).
- ✓ Balandrin M. F.; Kinghorn A. D.; Farnsworth N. R. (1993), In *Human Medicinal Agents from Plants*; Kinghorn A. D., Balandrin M. F., Eds.; American Chemical Society: Washington; chapter 1, p. 2-12.

- ✓ Balandrin, M. F., Klocke, J. A., Wurtele, E. S. and Bollinger, W. H. (1985). Natural Plant Chemicals: Sources of industrial and medicinal materials. *Science*, 228: 1154-1160.
- ✓ Banso A, Adeyemo SO (2007). Phytochemical and antimicrobial evaluation of ethanolic extract of *Dra-caena manni* Bark. *Nig. J. Biotech.* 18(1-2): 27-32.
- ✓ Banso A, Olutimayin T (2001). Phytochemical and antimicrobial evaluation of aqueous extracts of *Daniella oliveri* and *Nauclea latifolia*. *Nig. J. Biotech.* 12(1):114-118.
- ✓ Batovska, D. I., Todorova, I. T., Nedelcheva, D. V., Parushev, S. P., Atanassov, A. J., Hvarleva, T. D., Djakova, G. J., bankova, V. S. (2008). Preliminary study on biomarkers for the fungal residence in *Vitis vinifera* leaves, *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 165: 791-795. ISSN: 0176-1617
- ✓ Bauer A.W., Kirby E., Sherris E.M (1966). Antibiotic by standardized single disk method, *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.* 45 (4) 493–496.
- ✓ Bhagya Lakshmi Jyothi. K. (2013). Toxicity of agricultural herbicide 2, 4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid on growth, photosynthesis and respiration of rice field cyanobacterium. *International journal of scientific research.* Volume : 2 issue : 8 54-58
- ✓ Bhandari M J and Chandrashekar K R (2002). Glimpses of ethnic herbal medicine of costal Karnataka. *Ethnobotany.* Vol. 14 PP 1-12
- ✓ Biswa Nath Das, Achinto saha, Muniruddin Ahmed (2009). Anti-inflammatory activity of bark of *Xeromphis spinosa*. *Bangladesh Journal of Pharmacology.* 4: 76-78
- ✓ Blaxton JD, Der Marderosian A, Gibbs R (2002). Bioactive constituents of Alaskan devil's root *Oplonanax horridus*. *Economic Botany.* 56: 285-287.
- ✓ Boham BA, Kocipai AC (1974). Flavonoids and condensed tannins from leaves of *Hawaiian vaccinium vaticulatum* and *V. calycinium*. *Pacific Sci.* 48: 458-463.
- ✓ Borris, R.P. (1996). Natural productions research: Perspectives from a major pharmaceutical company. *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 51(1-3): 29-38.

- ✓ Brindha P, Sasikala, Purushoth (1977). Preliminary Phytochemical studies of higher plants. *Ethnobot.* 3: 84-96.
- ✓ Briskin DP. (2000). Medicinal plants and phytomedicines. Linking plant Biochemistry and Physiology to Human Health. *Plant Physiology* 124(2), 507-514.
- ✓ Brownlee, H.E., McEuen, A.R., Hedger, J. and Scott, I.M. (1990). Anti-fungal effects of cocoa tannin on the witches' broom pathogen (*Crinipellis pernicioso*). *Physiol. Mol. Plant Pathol.*, 36: 39-48.
- ✓ Cerutti, P. A. (1985). Prooxidant states and tumor promotion. *Science* 227, 375–381.
- ✓ Chabner BA, Horwitz SB (1999). Plant alkaloids in: Meyer, R, Pinedo H.M., Chabner B.A., *Cancer Chemotherapy and Biological Response Modifiers Annual* 18. Elsevier Science Publ. Co. p. 632
- ✓ Chand S. and Singh A. K. (2001). Direct somatic embryogenesis from zygotic embryos of a timber-yielding leguminous tree, *Hardwickia binata* Roxb. *Current Science.* 80: 882-887.
- ✓ Chandra D, Gupta S (1972). Anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic activity of volatile oil of *Curcuma longa* (Haldi). *Indian J Med Res.* 60:138-42
- ✓ Chandra Mohan S, Dinakar S, Anand T, Elayaraja R, Sathiya Priya B. (2012). Phytochemical, GC-MS analysis and Antibacterial activity of a Medicinal Plant *Acalypha indica* *Int. J. PharmTech Res.*4(3)
- ✓ Chaudhri (1996). *Indian Herbal Drug Industry: A Practical Approach to Industrial Pharmacognosy*, 1st ed., Eastern Publishers; New Delhi.
- ✓ ChemIDplus, *Oplopanone*, <https://chem.nlm.nih.gov/chemidplus/sid/0001911780>
- ✓ Chevallier, A. (1996). *The Encyclopedia of Medicinal Plants* Dorling Kindersley. London, ISBN 9- 780751-303148
- ✓ Chewonarin, T., Kinouchi, T., Kataoka, K., Arimachi, H., Kuwahara, T., Initkekumnuen, U. and Ohnishi, Y. (1999). Effects of Roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* Linn), a Thai medicinal plant, on the mutagenicity of various known mutagens. *Food Chemical and Toxicology*, 37: 591-601.

- ✓ Chopra, R. N.; Nayar, S. L.; Chopra I. C. (1956). Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, CSIR, New Delhi, India. 152, 162.
- ✓ Chopra, R.N., S.L. Nayar, and I.C. Chopra. (1986). Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants (Including the Supplement). Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi.
- ✓ Collin HA (2001). Secondary product formation in plant tissue cultures. *Plant Growth Regulation* 34:119–134
- ✓ Cos, P., Vlietinck, A.J., Vanden Berghe, D., and L. Maes (2006). Anti-infective potential of natural products: how to develop a stronger in vitro ‘proof-of concept’. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 106, 290–302.
- ✓ Costa M., Antonio M.A., Souza B.A.R.M (1999). Effects of prolonged administration of *Musa paradisiaca* L. (banana), an antiulcerogenic substance in rats. *Phytotherapy Research.* 11(1): 28-31.
- ✓ Cowman MM (1999). Plant products as antimicrobial agents. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.* 12: 561-582
- ✓ Cox, P (1990). Ethnopharmacology and the search for new drugs, in Chadurich, D. J., Marsh (ed) *Bioactive compounds from plants* (Ciba Foundation Symposium, 154) Chichester. 40-45.
- ✓ Cox, P. and Balick, M (1994). The ethnobotanical approaches to drug discovery. *Sci. Am. J.* 82-87.
- ✓ Cragg GM (2005). Newman DJ. Plants as source of anticancer agents. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2005; 100: 72-79.
- ✓ Cragg GM, Newman DJ, Snader KM. (1997). Natural products in drug discovery and development *J. Nat. Prod.* 60: 52.
- ✓ Dahanukar SA, Kulkarni RA, Rege NN (2000). Pharmacology of medicinal plants and natural products. *Ind. J. Pharmacol* 32:81
- ✓ Daiane Martins and Cecilia Veronica Nunez (2015). Secondary Metabolites from Rubiaceae Species. *Molecules,* 20, 13422-13495

- ✓ Daines, A.M., Payne, R.J., Humphries, M.E., Abell, A.D., (2003). The synthesis of naturally occurring Vitamin K and Vitamin K analogues. *Curr. Org. Chem.* 7, 1625–1634.
- ✓ Deori, S.L. and Khadabadi, S.S (2010). *In vitro* antihelmintic studies of *Chlorophytum borivilianum* Sant. & *Fernandez* tubers. *Ind. J. of Nat. Prod. Reso.* 1(1), 2010, (53-56).
- ✓ Dev, S. (1999). Ancient-modern concordance in Ayurvedic plants: some examples. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 107: 783-789.
- ✓ Dewick PM (2003) *Medicinal natural products, a biosynthetic approach* II Edition, John Wiley and Sons, Ltd, England:7
- ✓ Dey P, Dutta S and Chaudhuri TK. (2015). Comparative Phytochemical Profiling of *Clerodendrum infortunatum* L. Using GC-MS Method Coupled with Multivariate Statistical Approaches. *Metabolomics*. Volume 5, Issue 3, Pp-1-10
- ✓ Dharmendra Singh, Poonam Singh, Abhishek Gupta, Shikha Solank, Ekta sharma, Rajeev Nem (2012). Qualitative Estimation of the Presence of Bioactive Compound in *Centella asiatica*: An Important Medicinal Plant, *International Journal of Life Science and Medical Science*, Vol. 2 Iss. 1, PP. 5-7
- ✓ Diallo, D., B. Hveem, M.A. Mahmoud, G. Betge, B.S. Paulsen and A. Maiga. (1999). An ethnobotanical survey of herbal drugs of Gourma district, Mali. *Pharmaceutical Biol.*, 37: 80-91.
- ✓ Dr. Duke's Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical Database (Online).
- ✓ Dubey JP and Jones JL (2008). *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in humans and animals in the United States. *International Journal for Parasitology* 38 . 1257–1278
- ✓ Dubois MA, Benze SC (2000). New biologically triterpene, saponins from *Randia dumetorum*. *Planta Medica*. V (5); 451-5.
- ✓ Duke JA and Wain KK (1981). *Medicinal Plants of the world*. Computer Entries, 3: 1654
- ✓ Duke, J. A. (1985). *Handbook of medicinal herbs*. CRC Press, Inc., Boca Raton, Fla.

- ✓ Edeoga, HO, Okwu , DE and Mbaebie, BO(2005). Phytochemical constituents of some Nigerian medicinal plants, African J. Biotech 4(7): 685- 688
- ✓ Egunyomi A, Moody JO, Eletu OM (2009). Antisickling activities of two ethnomedicinal plant recipes used for the management of sickle cell anaemia in Ibadan, Nigeria. Afri. J. Biotechnol. 8(1): 020-025
- ✓ Elangevan V, Sekar N, Godndasamy S (1994). Chemopreventive Potential of Dietary Bioflavonoids against 20- Methylchofanthrene induced tumoringenesis. Cancer Lett. 87: 102-113.
- ✓ Elisabetsky E. (1991) Socio-political, economic and ethical issues in medicinal plants. J. Ethnopharmacol. 32: 235-239.
- ✓ El-Olemy MM, Al-Muhtadi FJ and Afifi AFA (1994). Experimental Phytochemistry: A laboratory manual. King Said University Press, Saudi Arabia, PP- 21-27.
- ✓ Emekli, A.E., Kasikci, E. and Yarat, A (2009). Effects of oleic acid on the tissue factor activity, blood lipids, antioxidant and oxidant parameters of streptozotocin induced diabetic rats fed a high-cholesterol diet. Med. Chem. Res. 56(9), 2009, (234-239).
- ✓ Eshrat, H.M. and A. Hussain. (2002). Hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic and antioxidant properties of combination of curcumin from *Curcuma longa*, and partially purified product from *Abroma augusta*, in streptozotocin induced diabetes. Indian J. Clin. Biochem. 17 (2): 33-43.
- ✓ Esposito, E., Rotilio, D., Di Matteo, V., Di Giulio, C., Cacchio, M., Algeri, S., (2002). A review of specific dietary antioxidants and the effects on biochemical mechanisms related to neurodegenerative processes. Neurobiol. Aging 23, 719–735.
- ✓ Farnsworth NR, Morris RW (1976). Higher plants: the sleeping giant of drug development. Am. J. Pharm., 48: 46-52.
- ✓ Farnsworth, N. R., and D. D. Soejarto. (1985). Potential consequences of plant extinction in the United States on the current and future availability of prescription drugs. Econ. Bot. 39(3):231-240

- ✓ Farnsworth, N.R. (1990) The Role of Ethno Pharmacology in Drug Development. Ciba Foundation Symposium 154. Bioactive Compounds from Plants. John Wiley & Sons, Baffins Lane, Chichester (England), 2-21.
- ✓ Farnsworth, N.R. and Soejarto, D.D. (1991). Global Importance of Medicinal Plants. J. Ethnopharmacol., 38,145-152
- ✓ Fa-Rong Yu, Xiu-Zhen Lian, Hong-Yun Guo, Peter M. McGuire, Ren-De Li, Rui Wang, Fa-Hong Yu., (2005). Isolation and characterization of methyl esters and derivatives from *Euphorbia kansui* (Euphorbiaceae) and their inhibitory effects on the human SGC-7901 cells. J Pharm Pharmaceut Sci. 8(3), 528-535.
- ✓ Fessenden RJ, Fessenden JS (1982). Organic Chemistry. 2nd edition. Willard Grand press. Boston. Mass
- ✓ Firm, R. (2010). Nature's Chemicals. Oxford University Press, Oxford. Pp 74-75
- ✓ Francavilla, M., Trotta, P., Luque, R., (2010). Phytosterols from *Dunaliella tertiolecta* and *Dunaliella salina*: a potentially novel industrial application. Bioresour. Technol. 101, 4144–4150.
- ✓ Freiburghaus F, Jonker SA, Nkuna MHN, Mwasunbi LB, Brun R (1997). In vitro trypanocidal activity of some rare Tanzanian medicinal plants. Acta Trop. 67: 181-185, 65-71
- ✓ Freiburghaus F, Kaminsky R, Nkunya MHH, Brun R (1996). Evaluation of Africa Medicinal Plants for their In-vitro trypanocidal activity. J. Ethnopharmacol., 55: 1-11.
- ✓ Garima Mandora, Satish Kant Sharma, Tarun Kant (2014). *In Vitro* Propagation and Field Establishment of *Hardwickia Binata* Roxb. And Assessment Polymorphism through Molecular Markers. J. Plant Develop. 21(2014): 23–31
- ✓ Gautam, S.; Singh, P.; Shivhare, Y. *Praecitrullus fistulosus* (2011). A Miraculous Plant. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Technology. 1, 9-12. 14
- ✓ Geissman TA (1963). Flavonoid compounds: tannins, lignins and related compounds. Vol. 9. Elsevier, New York. 1963, 265.
- ✓ Geissman, T.A. (1963). Flavonoid compounds, tannins, lignins and related compounds. In: Florkin M and Stotz EH (eds). New York, USA, Elsevier Press

- ✓ Gennari, C., Castoldi, D. and Sharon, O (2007). Natural products with taxol like antitumor activity. *Pure and Appl. Chem.* 79(2), 2007, (173-180).
- ✓ Ghildiyal R., K.V.R. Murthy, *Materials Research Bulletin*, 41, 1854-1860, 2006.
- ✓ Ghorpade RP, Chopra A, Nikam TD (2010) In vitro zygotic embryo germination and propagation of an endangered *Boswellia serrata* Roxb., a source of boswellic acid. *Physiol Mol Biol Plant* 16:159– 165
- ✓ Ghorpade RP, Chopra A, Nikam TD (2011) Influence of biotic and abiotic elicitors on four major isomers of boswellic acid in callus culture of *Boswellia serrata* Roxb. *Plant Omics J* 4:169–176
- ✓ Ghoshal S, Krishna BN, Lakshmi V (1996). Antiamoebic activity of piper longum fruits against *Entamoeba histolytica* in vitro and in vivo. *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 50: 167-170.
- ✓ Girish HV.and Satish S. (2000). Antibacterial Activity of Important Medicinal Plants on Phytopathogenic *Xanthomonas compestris* Pathovars. *Letters in Microbiology*,;28:145-147.
- ✓ Girisha.C, Sanjeevamurthy, and Gunti Rangasrinivas (2012). Tensile Properties Of Natural Fiber-Reinforced Epoxy-Hybrid Composites. *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER)* Vol.2, Issue.2, pp-471-474.
- ✓ Goyal S, Sharma P, Ramchandani U, Shrivastava S.K. and Dubey P.K (2011). Novel Anti-Inflammatory Topical Herbal Gels Containing *Withania somnifera* and *Boswellia serrata*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical & Biological Archives*, 2(4):1087-1094
- ✓ Guangchun Gao, Shuhua Qi, Si Zhang, Hao Yin, Zhihui Xiao, Minyi Li, Qingxin Li (2008). Minor compounds from the stem bark of Chinese mangrove associate *Catunaregam spinosa (thumb.) Tirven.* *Pharazie.* 2008: vol-63; 542-4.
- ✓ Guang-Chun Gao, Zhong-Xian Lu, Shu-Hong Tao, Si Zhang, Fa-Zuo Wang, and Qing-Xin Li (2011) . Triterpenoid saponins from the stem bark of *Catunaregam spinosa*. *Can. J. Chem.* 89: 1277–1282

- ✓ Gullece M, Aslan A, Sokmen M, Sahin F, Adiguzel A, Agar G, Sokmen A (2006). Screening the antioxidant and antimicrobial properties of the lichens *Parmelia saxatilis*. *Platismatia glauca*. *Ramalina pollinaria*. *Ramalina polymorpha* and *Umbilicaria nylanderian*. *Phytomedicine* 13: 515-521
- ✓ Gunaselvi G, Kulasekaren.V. Dr. V. Gopal (2010). Anti bacterial and antifungal activity of various leaves extracts of *Hardwickia binata* roxb. (Caesalpinaceae). *International Journal of PharmTech Research*. Vol.2, No.4, pp 2183-2187, Oct-Dec 2010
- ✓ Guven, K.C., Percot, A., Sezik, E., (2010). Alkaloids in marine algae. *Mar. Drugs* 8, 269–284.
- ✓ Hall, Iris; Wong, Oi; Reynolds, David; Chang, J. J. (2006). Hypolipidemic Effects of 2-Furoic Acid in Sprague-Dawley Rats. *Archiv der Pharmazie*. 3 (1): 15–23.
- ✓ Hamilton, A. (2003). Medicinal plants and conservation: issues Global health care challenge: Indian experiences and new prescriptions 220 and approaches [online]. UK, WWF, 2003 <http://www.wwf.org.uk/filelibrary/pdf/medplantsandcons.pdf>.
- ✓ Harborne JB. *Phytochemical Methods* (3rd Edn), (1993), Chapman and Hall , London, pp 49-188
- ✓ Harborne JB(1998). ‘Phytochemical methods: A guide to modern technique of plant analysis’, Chapman and Hall, London, 1998.
- ✓ Harborne, J.B. (1973). *Phytochemical Methods: A Guide to Modern Techniques of plant Analysis*. Chapman and Hall Ltd., London. P. 279.
- ✓ Harun-ur-Rashid, M., Gafur, M.A., Sadik, G.M. and Rahman, M.A (2002). Biological activities of a new acrylamide derivative from *Ipomea turpitem*. *Pak. J. of Biol. Sci.* 5(9), 2002, (968-969).
- ✓ Harvey AL (2008) Natural products in drug discovery. *Drug Discovery Today* 13:894–901
- ✓ Harvey AL, (1993). An introduction to drugs from natural products. In *Drugs From Natural Products*, Harvey AL (ed), Ellis Horwood Limited, Chinchester, 1-6.

- ✓ Harvey AL, (2000). Strategies for discovering drugs from previously unexplored natural products. *Drug Discovery Today*, 5, 7, 294-300.
- ✓ Haslam, E. (1996). Natural polyphenols (vegetable tannins) as drugs and medicines: possible modes of action. *Journal of Natural Products*, 59, 205-215
- ✓ Hassan, A.A.B., Abdel-Rafei, M.K. and Hasan, H.F. (2016). Evaluation of radiosensitizing and antiangiogenesis activity of *Chelidonium majus* extract in ehrlich ascites carcinoma transplanted mice. *Pakistan J. Zool.*, 48: 1665-1674.
- ✓ Hawley GG (1981). *The Condensed Chemical Dictionary* 10th ed. Van Nostrand Reinhold Co. p. 416.
- ✓ Hemangi Rajput (2013). Effects of *Atropa belladonna* as an Anti-Cholinergic. *Natural Products Chemistry and Research*. 2013, 1:1 pp-1-2.
- ✓ Hemerski L, Furlan M, Silva DHS, Cavalheiro AJ, Eberlin MN, Tomazela DM, Bolzani VS (2003). Iridoid glucosides from *Randia spinosa* (Rubiaceae) *Phytochem*. 2003: Vol-63 ; 397-400.
- ✓ Henkel T, Brunne RM, Muller H, Reichel F. (1999). Potentials of oregano for biological weed control. *Angewandte Chemie. International Edition*, 643.
- ✓ Hernandez-Vázquez, L., Mangas, S., Palazón, J. & Navarro-Ocaña, A. (2010) Valuable medicinal plants and resins: Commercial phytochemicals with bioactive properties, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 31: 476-480.
- ✓ Hertog MGL, Feskens EJM, Hollman DCH, Katan MB, Kromhout D (1993). Dietary antioxidant flavonoids and risk of coronary heart disease. The Zutphen Elderly study. *Lancet* 342: 1077-1011.
- ✓ Hesata S, Nishimura A, Kawamura I, Inouye H (1982). Four Iridoids from *Randia Canthioides*. *Phytochem*; Vol (2); 353 – 7.
- ✓ Hironori Tsuchiya (2017). Review Anesthetic Agents of Plant Origin: A Review of Phytochemicals with Anesthetic Activity. *Molecules* 22, 1369, PP-1-34.
- ✓ Hoareau L and E J Dasilva (1999). Medicinal Plant: A re-emerging medicinal aid. *Elect. J. Biotechnol.*, 2:56-70.

- ✓ Hogan JC. (1997). Combinatorial chemistry in drug discovery. *Nature Biotechnology*, 15:328.
- ✓ Holanda Pinto SA, Pinto LM, Cunha GM, Chaves MH, Santos FA, Rao VS (2008). Anti-inflammatory effect of alpha, beta-amyrin, a pentacyclic triterpene from *Protium heptaphyllum* in rat model of acute periodontitis. *Inflammopharmacology*. 16: 48-52. 10.1007/s10787-007-1609-x .
- ✓ Hosseini-Sharifabad M. and Esfandiari F. (2014), Effect of *Boswellia serrata* gum resin on the memory of hippocampus CA1 pyriamidal cells in aged rat. *Phytopharm*. Vol. 15, No. 03, PP-31.
- ✓ Hostettmann K, Hamburger M (1991). *Phytochem*. 30(12): 3864-3874 Oliver-Bever B (1986). *Medicinal Plants in Tropical West Africa*, London, Cambridge Univ. Press. p.134.
- ✓ Hostettmann, K. and A. Marston, (1995). *Saponins Chemistry and Pharmacology of Natural Products*. University Press, Cambridge.
- ✓ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32012R0872>
- ✓ <http://www.icca-chem.org/en/Home/ICCA-initiatives/global-product-strategy/>
- ✓ <http://www.nist.gov/srd/nist1a.cfm>
- ✓ <https://chem.nlm.nih.gov/chemidplus/sid/0019044065>
- ✓ <https://echa.europa.eu/>
- ✓ <https://phytochem.nal.usda.gov/phytochem/search>
- ✓ <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- ✓ Hucker, B.; Varelis, P. (2011). "Thermal decarboxylation of 2-furoic acid and its implication for the formation of furan in foods". *Food Chemistry*. 126 (3): 1512–1513.
- ✓ Hugo WB, Russel AD (1984). *Pharmaceutical Microbiology*, Blackwell Scientific Publications, Third edition pp. 179-200.
- ✓ Hunt, J. (2002). "Early developments in petroleum geochemistry". *Organic Geochemistry*. 33: 1025–1052.

- ✓ Ibrahim M. and Abd-El-Aal M., (2008) Spectroscopic study of Heavy Metals Interaction with Organic Acid, *Int. J. Environment and Pollution*, 35(1), 99-110
- ✓ Ibrahim, D. and Osman, H. (1995). Antimicrobial activity of *Cassia alata* from Malaysia, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 45: 151-156.
- ✓ Jain, S.K. (1968). Medicinal plants. National Book Trust New Delhi. pp 256.
- ✓ Jain, S.K. (1967). Plants in Indian Medicine and Folk lore associated with healing of bones'. In *Ind. J.Orthopedics* 1: pp. 95-104.
- ✓ Jayakumar M and Manikandan M (2005). Allelopathic potential of *Acacia leucopholea* on groundnut and sorghum. Proc. IV. World Allelopathy congress Charles sturt University Eds.: Australia.
- ✓ Jeevan Ram A and VenkataRaju R.R (2001). Certain potential crud drug used by tribal's of Nallamalias, Andhra Pradesh for skin disease. *Ethnobotany*, Vol 13, PP 110-115.
- ✓ Jeng, W.L., Huh, C.A., (2004). Lipids in suspended matter and sediments from the East China Sea shelf. *Org. Geochem.* 35 (5), 647–660.
- ✓ Jhariya M. K. And Oraon P. R.. (2012). Analysis of herbaceous diversity in fire affected areas of Bhoramdeo wildlife sanctuary, Chhattisgarh. *The International quaternary journal of life science*, 7(2) : 325-330.
- ✓ John Coates (2000). Interpretation of Infrared Spectra, In: A practical approach. *Encyclopedia of Analytical Chemistry*. R.A.Meyers (Ed.). Johnwiley and Sons Ltd; pp 10815-837.
- ✓ Joy, P.P., Thomas, J., Mathew, S., and Skaria, B.P. (2001). Medicinal Plants. *Tropical Horticulture* Vol. 2. Naya Prokash, Calcutta 449- 632.
- ✓ Kamato, G., Zyl, E., Vuuren, S.F., Figueiredo, A.C., Barroso, J.G., Pedro L.G. and Viljoen, A.M. (2008). Seasonal variation in essential oil composition, oil toxicity and the biological activity of solvent extracts of three South African *Salvia* species. *Af. J. of Botany*. 74, 2008, (230-237).
- ✓ Kamboj V. P. (2000). Herbal medicine. *Current Science*, VOL. 78, NO. 1, PP 35-39

- ✓ Kangogo K. Geoffrey, Kagira M. John, Maina Naomi and Karanja M. Simon (2014). Qualitative Phytochemical Screening of *Camellia sinensis* and *Psidium guajava* Leave Extracts from Kericho and Baringo Counties, International Journal of Advanced Biotechnology and Research(IJBR), Vol5, Issue3 p506-512.
- ✓ Kar, A. (2007). Pharmacognosy and Pharmacobiotechnology (Revised-Expanded Second Edition). New Age International Limited Publishers New Delhi. pp 332-600.
- ✓ Karthika K, Jamuna S, Paulsamy S (2014). TLC and HPTLC Fingerprint Profiles of Different Bioactive Components from the Tuber of *Solena amplexicaulis*. Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry ; 3 (1): 198-206.
- ✓ Kashem Liton A, Rabiul Islam M (2006). Condensation reaction of benzyl with resorcinol and the establishment of the spectral data as well as cytotoxicity study. Bangladesh J. Pharmacol. 1:58-63.
- ✓ Kazmi, M. H., A. Malik, S. Hameed, N. Akhtar, and S. Noor Ali. (1994). Phytochemistry 36:761–763.
- ✓ Khanum, F., Husnain, T. and Riazuddin, S (1998). Effect of age of seedling and phytohormones on micropropagation of indica rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) from meristem culture. J. Plant Biol. 41(2): 93-96.
- ✓ Kimmatkar N, Thawani V, Hingorani L, (2003). Efficacy and tolerability of *Boswellia serrata* extract in treatment of osteoarthritis of knee - a randomized double blind placebo controlled trial.
- ✓ Kiritikar KR, Basu BD. (1975). Indian Medicinal Plants. 2nd ed. Vol 4. New Delhi: Jayyed Press.
- ✓ Knekt, P.; Järvinen, R.; Reunanen, A.; Maatela, J. (1996). Flavonoid intake and coronary mortality in Finland: a cohort study. Br. Med. J. 312, 478-481.
- ✓ Kokate, C.K., (1994). Practical Pharmacognosy, Vallabh Prakashan, 4, 29.
- ✓ Kokate, C.K., Khandelwal, K.R., Pawar, A.P., Gokhale, S.B., (1995), Practical Pharmacognosy, Nirali Prakashan, 1, 11 – 19.

- ✓ Komal Kumar J. and Devi Prasad A.G. (2011). Identification and comparison of biomolecules in medicinal plants of *Tephrosiatinctoria* and *Atylosiaalbicansby* using FTIR, Romanian J. Biophys, 21(1), 63-71 (2011)
- ✓ Kong JM, Goh NK, Chia LS, Chia TF. (2003). Recent advances in traditional plant drugs and orchids Acta Pharmacol. Sin. 24: 7. Newman DJ, Cragg GM, Snader KM.
- ✓ Kong, A., McCullagh, P., Meng, X.-L., Nicolae, D., Tan, Z., (2003). A theory of statistical models for Monte Carlo integration (with discussion). J. Roy. Statist. Soc. B 65, 585–618.
- ✓ Krishna P. Panchal, Neeta R. Pandya, Susy Albert, Dhara J. Gandhi. (2014). A x-ray image analysis for assessment of forage seed quality. International journal of plant, animal and environmental sciences. Vol 4 issue pp 103-109.
- ✓ Krishnaiah D, Sarbatly R, Bono A (2007). Phytochemical antioxidants for health and medicine – A move towards nature. Biotechnol. Mol. Biol, Rev., 1(4): 097-104.
- ✓ Krishnaswamy K (2008). Traditional Indian spices and their health significance. Asia Pac J Clin Nutr: 17: 265-8.
- ✓ Kubo M, Kimura Y, Shin H, Haneda T, Tani,T, Namba K (1981). Studies on the antifungal substance of crude drug (II) on the roots of *Polygonum cupsidatum* Sieb. Et Zucc (Polygonaceae). Sho- yakugaku Zasshi, 1981; 35: 58—61.
- ✓ Kulkarni, D.K. and Upadhye A. S. (2006). Indigenous knowledge of biodiversity used for sustainable development. In Economic botany (Ed. Dr, (Mrs.) Sampat Nehera) Pointer Publisher, Jaipur, India, 242-257
- ✓ Kumar H, Kawai T, Akira S (2011) Pathogen recognition by the innate immune system. Int Rev Immunol 30:16–34
- ✓ Kumar, B., Vijayakumar, M., Govindarajan, R.P and Ushpangadan, P. (2007). Ethnopharmacological approaches to wound healing exploring medicinal plants of India. J. Ethnopharmacol. 114, (103-113).
- ✓ Kundu, A, Bagchi, S and Kundu, D. (1999). ‘Regional Distribution of Infrastructure and Civic Amenities in Urban India’, Economic and Political Weekly 34, pp 1893-1906 .

- ✓ Laird, S.A. and Pierce, A.R. (2002). Promoting Sustainable and Ethical Botanicals: Strategies to Improve Commercial Raw Material Sourcing. Rainforest Alliance, New York (available online at: www.rainforest-alliance.org/news/archives/news/news44.html).
- ✓ Lee SH, Choi SY, Kim H, Hwang JS, Lee BG, Gao JJ (2002). Mulberroside F isolated from the leaves of *Morus alba* inhibits melanin biosynthesis. *Biol. Pharm. Bull.* 25:1045-1048.
- ✓ Lei Guo, Jin-zhong Wu, Ting Han, Tong Cao, Khalid Rahman and Lu-ping Qin. (2008). Chemical Composition, Antifungal and Antitumor Properties of Ether Extracts of *Scapania verrucosa* Heeg. and its Endophytic Fungus *Chaetomium fusiforme*. *Molecules*, 13, 2114-2125; DOI: 10.3390/molecules13092114.
- ✓ Léopold TN, (2010). Antifungal properties of essential oils and some constituents to reduce food borne pathogen, *Journal of Yeast and Fungal Research*, 1(1):001-008.
- ✓ Leung AY, Foster S (1996). *Encyclopedia of common natural ingredients used in food, drugs and cosmetics*. 2nd ed. New York: John Wiley and Sons; 1996. p. 389-91
- ✓ Li, L. (2000) Opportunity and Challenge of Traditional Chinese Medicine in Face of the Entrance to WTO (World Trade Organization). *Chinese Journal of Information on Traditional Chinese Medicine*, 7, 7-8.
- ✓ Liliana Hernández Vázquez, Javier Palazon and Arturo Navarro-Ocaña (2012). The Pentacyclic Triterpenes amyryns: A Review of Sources and Biological Activities, *Phytochemicals - A Global Perspective of Their Role in Nutrition and Health*, Dr Venketeshwer Rao (Ed.), ISBN: 978-953-51-0296-0, InTech, Available from: <http://www.intechopen.com/books/phytochemicals-a-global-perspective-of-their-role-in-nutrition-andhealth/the-pentacyclic-triterpenes-amyryns-a-review-of-sources-and-biological-activities>
- ✓ Lukhoba, C.W., Simmonds, M.S.J. and Paton, A.J. (2006). A review of Ethnobotanical uses. *Ethnopharmacol.* 103, 2006, (124).
- ✓ Lyman WJ (1982). *Handbook of Chemical Property Estimation Methods* NY: McGraw-Hill pp. 4-9, 7-6, 8-12

- ✓ Madziga HA, Sanni S and Sandabe UK. (2010). Phytochemical and Elemental Analysis of *Acalypha wilkesiana* Leaf. *Journal of American Science*. 6(11): 510-514.
- ✓ Mander M (1998). Medicinal plant marketing in Bushbuckridge and Mpumalanga: A market survey and recommended strategies for sustaining the supply of plants in the region. Unpublished report. Darudec and DWAF, South Africa.
- ✓ Maregesi, S. M., L. Pieters, O. D. Ngassapa, S. Apers, R. Vingerhoets, P. Cos, D. A. V. Berghe and A. J. Vlietinck (2008). Screening of Some Tanzanian Medicinal Plants from Bunda District for Antibacterial, Antifungal and Antiviral Activities. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 119, 58-66.
- ✓ Marino, M. and Bersani, C. (1999) Antimicrobial Activity of the Essential Oils of *Thymus vulgaris* L. Measured Using a Bioimpedometric Method. *Journal of Food Protection*, 62, 1017-1023.
- ✓ Martinez, M.J.A.; Lazaro, R.M, del Olmo LMB. & Benito, P.B. (2008) Anti-infectious activity in the anthemideae tribe. In: Atta-ur- (Ed.) *Studies in Natural Products Chemistry*, Vol. 35. Elsevier. pp 445-516
- ✓ Mathai K. (2000). Nutrition in the Adult Years. In Krause's *Food, Nutrition, and Diet Therapy*, 10th ed., ed. L.K. Mahan and S. Escott-Stump, American Cancer Society. : 271: 274-275.
- ✓ Maupetit P (1984). New constituents in *Olibanum resinoid* and essential oils. *Perfumer Flavorist* 1984;9:19-37.
- ✓ Maurya, R.; Singh G. & Yadav, P.P. (2008). Antiosteoporotic agents from Natural sources. In: Atta-ur-Rahman (Ed.) *Studies in Natural Products Chemistry*, Vol. 35. Elsevier. pp 517-545.
- ✓ Mc Devitt, J., Balboni, J., Garcia, L., & Gu, J. (2001). Consequences for victims: a comparison of bias and non bias motivated assaults. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 45(4), 697-713.
- ✓ Mc Laughlin, J.L. (1991). Crown gall tumors on potato discs and brine shrimp lethality: two single bioassays for plant screening and fractionation. *Acad. Press, London*. 6, (1-31).

- ✓ McGinty, D., Letizia, C.S., Api, A.M., (2010). Fragrance material review on phytol. Food Chem. Toxicol. 48, S59–S63. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2009.11.012>.
- ✓ Meenakshi S and Manicka Gnanambigai D, Tamil mozhi S, Arumugam M, Balasubramanian T (2009). Total flavonoid and *invitro* antioxidant activity of two seaweeds of Rameshwaram coast. Global Journal of Pharmacology. 3(2): 59-62.
- ✓ Mehta RG, Murillo G, Naithani R, Peng X (2010). Cancer chemoprevention by natural products: how far have we come Pharm Res, 27: 950-61.
- ✓ Mendelsohn, R. W. Nordhaus, and D. Shaw (1999). “The impact of climate variation on US agriculture” in R. Mendelsohn and J. Neumann (eds) The Impact of Climate Change on the United States Economy. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- ✓ Merlin N.J., Parthasarathy V., Manavalan R. and Kumaravel S (2009). Chemical Investigation of Aerial Parts of *Gmelinaasiatica* Linn by GC-MS, Pharmacognosy Res, 1(3), 152-156 (2009).
- ✓ Meyer J P, Stanley D J, Herscovitch L and Topolnytsky L (2002), “Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to the Organization: A Meta-analysis of Antecedents, Correlates, and Consequences”, Journal of Vocational Behavior, Vol. 61, pp. 20-52.
- ✓ Middleton EJ and Kandaswami C (1994) Potential health promoting properties of citrus flavonoids. Food Technol. 18:115–120.
- ✓ Mikaeil, B.; Maatooq, G.; Badria, F.; Amer, (2003). M. Chemistry and immunomodulatory activity of frankincense oil. Z. Naturforsch., C, J. Biosci. 2 58, 230-238.
- ✓ Mirza, Z. S., Nadeem, M. S., Beg, M. A., Sulehria, A. Q. K., & Shah, S. I., (2012). Current status of fisheries in Mangla Reservoir, Pakistan. Biologia, 58(1&2): 31-39.
- ✓ Mohammad Abdul Motalib Momin, Sm Faysal Bellah, Sarder Mohammad Raussel Rahman, Ahmed Ayedur Rahman, Gazi Mohammad Monjur Murshid, Sarder Mohammad Saker Billah, Talha Bin Emran (2014)., Phytopharmacological evaluation of ethanol extract of *Sida cordifolia* L. Roots. Asian Pac J Trop Biomed; 4(1): 18-24doi:10.1016/S2221-1691(14)60202-1.

- ✓ Mohan Biikram Gewalii (2008). Aspects of traditional medicine in Nepal. Institute of natural medicine, university of Tehama.
- ✓ Mojab F, Kamalinejad M, Ghaderi N, Vahidipour HR, (2003). Phytochemical screening of some species of Iranian plants. Iran. J. Pharm. Res. 2: 77-82.
- ✓ Moorachian, M. E. (2000). Phytochemicals: Why and How? Tastings. 4-5
- ✓ Mouhssen Lahlou (2013). The Success of Natural Products in Drug Discovery. Pharmacology & Pharmacy, 4, 17-31.
- ✓ Movalia Dharmishtha and Gajera Falguni (2009). Antibacterial Activity of Methanolic Fruit Extract of *Randia dumetorum* Lamk. International Journal of Pharm Tech Research. Vol.1, No.3, pp 679-681.
- ✓ Mukherjee PK, Wahile A (2006). Integrated approaches towards drug development from Ayurveda and other Indian system of medicines. J Ethnopharmacol., 103: 25-35
- ✓ Mukherjee PW (2002). Quality Control of Herbal Drugs: An Approach to Evaluation of Botanicals. Business Horizons Publishers, New Delhi, India.
- ✓ Mukherjee, P.K. and Wahile, A. (2006). Integrated approaches towards drug development from Ayurveda and other Indian system of medicines. J. Ethnopharmacol. 103: 25-35.
- ✓ Mulugeta L., Tarekegn A., and Olsson M., (2003). Gum and resin resources from some *Acacia*, *Boswellia* and *Commiphora* species and their economic contribution in Liban, Southeastern Ethiopia. Journal of Arid Environments 55, 465-482.
- ✓ Muralidhar Roa D and Pullaiah T. (2001). Ethno medico-botanical studies in Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh, India. Ethnobotany. Vol. 13, PP 40-44.
- ✓ Nagesh, K. S. & Shanthamma, C. (2009). Antibacterial activity of *Curculigo orchioides* rhizome extract on pathogenic bacteria. African Journal of Microbiology Research 3(1):005 – 009.
- ✓ Naira Nayeem , Karvekar M D (2010). Isolation of phenolic compounds from the methanolic extract of *Tectona grandis*. Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and chemical Sciences. ; 1(2):221-225.

- ✓ Namdeo A, Mahadik R, Kadam S (2006) Cost effective medium for callus initiation from *Catharanthus roseus* leaves. *Pharmacogn Mag* 2: 227-231.
- ✓ Namratha Pai Kotebagilu, Vanitha Reddy Palvai, and Asna Urooj (2014). Protective Effect of Selected Medicinal Plants against Hydrogen Peroxide Induced Oxidative Damage on Biological Substrates. *Int J Med Chem*. 2014; 861084.
- ✓ Narasinga Rao. (2003). Bioactive phytochemicals in Indian foods and their potential in health promotion and disease prevention. *Asia Pacific Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 12 (1): 9 - 22.
- ✓ Narayana, D.B.A., Katayar, C.K. and Brindavanam, N.B. (1998). Original system: search, research or re-search. *IDMA Bull*. 29: 413-416.
- ✓ Narayanaswamy V (1981). Origin And Development Of Ayurveda. *Ancient Science of Life*, Vol. I, No.1, PP-1-7
- ✓ Navneet K. Singh, Arun K. Mishra¹, Jeetendra K. Gupta, S. Jayalakshmi (2010). *Randia Spinosa* (POIR.): Ethnobotany, Phytochemistry And Pharmacology -A Review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*. Volume 4, Issue 1 Article 023.
- ✓ Nayak, A. R., Chaudhury, D. and Reddy, J. N. (2004). Genetic divergence in scented rice. *Oryza*, 41: 79-82
- ✓ Ncube N, Afolayan SAJ, Okoh AI (2008). Assessment techniques of antimicrobial properties of natural compounds of plant origin: current methods and future trends. *Afr. J. Biotechnol*. 7(12): 1797-1806.
- ✓ Nenaah, G (2013). Antimicrobial activity of *Calotropis procera* Ait. (Asclepiadaceae) and isolation of four flavonoid glycosides as the active constituents. *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*, v.29, n.7, p.1255- 1262, 2013.
- ✓ Netscher, T., (2007). Synthesis of vitamin E. *Vitam. Horm*. 76, 155–202.
- ✓ Newman, D.J., Crag, G.M. and Snader, K.M. (2000). The Influence of Natural Products upon Drug Discovery. *Natural Product Reports*, 17, 215-234

- ✓ Nishanta R, Harris CS, Towers GHN (2002). Antimicrobial activity of plants collected from serpentine outcrops in Sri Lanka. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 40(3): 235–244.
- ✓ Nishanta Rajakaruna, Cory S. Harris and G.H.N. Towers (2002). Antimicrobial Activity of Plants Collected from Serpentine Outcrops in Sri Lanka, *Pharmaceutical Biology*. Vol. 40, No. 03, pp. 235–244.
- ✓ Nwogu LA, Igwe CU, Emejulu AA (2008). Effects of *Landolphia owariensis* leaf extract on the liver function profile and haemoglobin concentration of albino rats. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.*, 2(12): 240-242.
- ✓ Obadoni BO, Ochuko PO (2001). Phytochemical studies and comparative efficacy of the crude extract of some homeostatic plants in Edo and Delta states of Nigeria. *Global J. Pure Appl. Sci.*, 8: 203- 208.
- ✓ Odebiyi A and Sofowora AE (1978). Phytochemical screening of Nigerian medicinal plants. *Lloydia* 41(3): 234-246.
- ✓ Okwu, D.E. (2004). Phytochemicals and vitamin content of indigenous spices of South Eastern Nigeria. *J. Sustain. Agric. Environ.* 6: 30-34
- ✓ Okwu, D.E.(2005). Phytochemicals, Vitamins and Mineral contents of two Nigeria Medicinal plants. *Int. J. Mol. Med. Adv. Sci.* 1(4): 375- 381.
- ✓ Olaleye MT (2007). Cytotoxicity and antibacterial activity of methanolic extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa*. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 1(1): 009-013.
- ✓ Omulokoli E, Khan B, Chhabra SC (1997). Antiplasmodial activity of four Kenyan medicinal plants. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 56: 133-137.
- ✓ Orwa C, A Mutua, Kindt R , Jamnadass R, S Anthony. (2009). Agroforestree Database: a tree reference and selection guide version 4.0 (<http://www.worldagroforestry.org/sites/treedbs/treedatabases.asp>).
- ✓ Oueslatia, S., Ksouri, R., Falleh, H., Pichette, A., Abdelly, C., Legault, J., (2012). Phenolic content, antioxidant, anti inflammatory and anticancer activities of the edible halophyte *Suaeda fruticosa* Forssk. *Food Chem.* 132, 943–947.

- ✓ Owolabi J., Omogbai E.K.I. and Obasuyi O (2007). Antifungal and antibacterial activities of the ethanolic and aqueous extract of *Kigella africana* (Bignoniaceae) stem bark. *Afr.J. Biotechnol.* 6: 882-885
- ✓ Pachamuthu, K.; Schmidt, R. R (2006). Synthetic routes to thiooligosaccharides and thioglycopeptides. *Chem. Rev.* , 106, 160-187.
- ✓ Padulosi S, Leaman D, Quek P (2002) Challenges and opportunities in enhancing the conservation and use of medicinal and aromatic plants. *J Herbs Spices Med Plants* 9: 243-267.
- ✓ Paramanatham, M and. Murugesan, A. (2014). GC-MS analysis of *Holarrhena antidysentrica* Wall Flower. *International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research (IJSETR)*, Volume 3, Issue 3, PP-630-639.
- ✓ Pardhy,R. S.; Bhattacharyya, S. C (1978). β -Boswellic acid, Acetyl- β -boswellic acid, Acetyl-11-keto- β - boswellic acid and 11-Keto- β -boswellic acid, Four Pentacyclic Triterpene Acids from the Resin of *Boswellia serrata* Roxb. *Ind. J. Chem.* , 16B, 176-178.
- ✓ Pasquale DE (1984). Pharmacognosy: the oldest modern science *J. Ethnopharmacology* ; 11:1.
- ✓ Patel Ritesh G, Pathak Nimish L, Rathod Jaimik D, Dr.L.D.Patel and Bhatt Nayna M (2011). Phytopharmacological Properties of *Randia dumetorum* as a Potential Medicinal Tree: An Overview. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science* 01 (10); 24-26.
- ✓ Patil MB and Khan PA (2015). Ethnomedicinal Studies Of *Acalypha indica* L. (Euphorbiaceae). *Review of Research Journal*, 4 (7) 1-6.
- ✓ Patil MB and Khan PA (2017). "Primary Phytochemical Studies of *Catunaregam spinosa* (Thunb.) Tirven for Secondary Metabolites". *Int J Pharm Bio Sci* 8(2): 320-323.
- ✓ Patil MB And Ramaiah PV (2006) "Clinical Scrutiny of Leaves of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. (Moringaceae) of known Anti-Diabetic Potential. 'Bioinfolet'. 3 (4), 246-250.

- ✓ Patil MB And Ramaiah PV (2006). “Ethnobotany In Human Health Care Of Nandurbar District In Maharashtra, India. Bioinfolet’. Vol. 3 (2), 133-135.
- ✓ Patil MB. (2009). Plants Used In Rheumatism By Tribal Peoples Of Nandurbar District Of Maharashtra, India. Biozone’ Vol. 1 (1), 45-50.
- ✓ Pawar RK, Sharma S, Singh KC, Sharma RK (2011). Physico-chemical standardization and development of HPTLC method for the determination of β -boswellic acid from *Boswellia serrata* Roxb. (exudate). Int J App Pharm ;3:8-13.
- ✓ Pawar S and Patil D A (2008). Ethnobotany of Jalgaon district: Daya Publishing Houses, New Delhi. PP 8-9.
- ✓ Perrett, D. I., Lee, K. J., Penton-Voak, I., Rowland, D., Yoshikawa, S., Burt, D. M., Henzi, S. P., Castles, D. L. & Akamatsu, S. (1998). Effects of sexual dimorphism on facial attractiveness. Nature 394, 884–887.
- ✓ Phillipson JD, O’Neill MJ. (1987). Antimalarial and amoebicidal natural products. In: Hostettmann K, Lea PJ (Eds.) Biologically Active Natural Products. pp. 49-64, Oxford, Clarendon Press.
- ✓ Piyush Ranjan Mishra, Prasanna Kumar Panda, Korla Apanna Chowdary and Saswati Panigrahi (2012). Antidiabetic and Antihypelipidaemic Activity of *Randia dumetorum*. International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Chemistry. 2(3). PP-
- ✓ Poly Tikadar, Sharat K Palita and Debabrata Panda (2017). Phytochemical analysis of medicinal plants used for treatment of dysentery and diarrhoea by the Paraja Tribe of Koraput, Odisha, India. International Journal of Herbal Medicine. 5(2): 01-04
- ✓ Potts and Kirk (1983). Indicates that erucamide should be immobile in soil (Swann .RL 1983).
- ✓ Prabakaran R, Senthil Kumar T and Rao M V. (2014) GC-MS Analysis and In vitro Cytotoxicity Studies of Root Bark Exudates of *Hardwickia binata* Roxb. American Journal of Phytomedicine and Clinical Therapeutics. 2 6 723-733.

- ✓ Prakash, P. and Gupta, N. (2005) Therapeutic Uses of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn (Tulsi) with a Note on Eugenol and Its Pharmacological Actions: A Review. Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology, 49, 125-131.
- ✓ PubChem: Data deposited in or computed by Pub Chem <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- ✓ R'ios JL, Recio MC (2005). Medicinal plants and antimicrobial activity. J. Ethnopharm. 100: 80–84.
- ✓ Rabe, T. and Staden, J.V. (1997). Antibacterial activity of South African plants used for medicinal purposes. J. Ethnopharmacol. 56: 81-87.
- ✓ Raghavaiah, V (1962). The Yanadis. Bharatiya Adimajati Sevak Sangh, New Delhi.
- ✓ Raja Reddy K. Das VSR (2001). Physiological Studies of Some Semiarid Scrub Species. Indian J. Experimental Bio. :Vol 19; 256- 260
- ✓ Raju V K (2003). Susruta of Ancient India. Indian J Ophthalmol, 51:119-22
- ✓ Raju VK (1994). Antiquity of Indian Medicine: Excerpts from Charaka Club. Proceedings of the Cogan Ophthalmological Historical Society, Vol II.
- ✓ Ramakrishnappa, K. (2002). Impact of cultivation and gathering of medicinal plants on biodiversity: case studies from India. In: Biodiversity and the Ecosystem.
- ✓ Ramesh Marasini, Susan Joshi, (2012). Antibacterial and Antifungal Activity of Medicinal Orchids Growing in Nepal. J Nepal Chem Soc. 29.
- ✓ Raskin, I., Ribnicky, D.M., Komarnytsky, S., Ilic, N., Poulev, A., Borisjuk, N., Brinker, A., Moreno, D.A., Ripoll, C., Yakoby, N., O'Neal, J.M., Cornwell, T., Pastor, I. and Fridlender, B. (2002). Plants and human health in the twenty-first century. Trends Biotechnol. 20: 522-531.
- ✓ Ravan, P.H. (1998). Medicinal plants and global sustainability: the canary in the coal mine. In medicinal plants: a global heritage, proceedings of the international conference on medicinal plants for survival, New Delhi; International Development Research Center, 14-18.

- ✓ Ravi Upadhyay and Chauhan S. V. (2000), Ethnobotanical observation on Koya tribe of Gundalamandal of Khammam District, Andhra Pradesh. Ehtnanobotany, Vol. 12 PP 93-109
- ✓ Ray S. And Sainkhediya J. (2012). Diversity of grasses in nimar region, madhya pradesh. Indian journal of plant sciences. Vol. 1 (2-3) jul.-sept. & oct.-dec., pp. 144-152.
- ✓ Ray S. And Sainkhediya J. (2014). Threatened weeds of bt cotton field innimar region of madhya pradesh. Asian journal of bio science, volume 9, issue 1 pp 84-87.
- ✓ Reddy PS, Jamil K, Madhusudhan P (2001). Antibacterial activity of isolates from Piper longum and *Taxus baccata*. J. Pharmaceutical Biol. 39: 236-238.
- ✓ Rivera JO, Loya AM, Ceballos R (2013) Use of Herbal Medicines and Implications for Conventional Drug Therapy Medical Sciences. Altern Integ Med 2: 130.
- ✓ Rohit Bhattacharya , Reddy KRC and Mishra AK (2014). Export strategy of Ayurvedic Products from India. International Journal of Ayurvedic Medicine. 5(1), 125-128.
- ✓ Roja G, Rao PS. (2000) Anticancer compounds from tissue cultures of Medicinal plant. Journal Herbs spices Med. Plants 7 :71-102.
- ✓ Rosangkima G, Prasad SB, (2004). Antitumor activity of some plants from Meghalaya and Mizoram against murine ascites Dalton's lymphoma. Indian J Exptl Biol, 42: 981-988.
- ✓ Rosangkima, G and Jagetia, GC. (2015). In Vitro Anticancer Screening Of Medicinal Plants Of Mizoram State, India, Against Dalton's Lymphoma, Mcf-7 And Hela Cells. International Journal of Recent Scientific Research Vol. 6, Issue, 8, pp.5648-5653.
- ✓ Rosenthal GA, (1991). The biochemical basis for the deleterious effects of L-canavanine. Phytochemistry, 30: 1055-1058.
- ✓ Rota, M.C., Herrera, A., Martinez, R.M., Sotomayor, J.A. and Jordan, M.J. (2008). Antimicrobial activity and chemical composition of *Thymus vulgaris*, *Thymus zygis* and *Thymus hyemalis* essential oils. Food Control. 19, (681-687).

- ✓ Rothe S.P., Sapkal S.S., Maheshwari A.A. (2017). Traditional ethnomedicinal investigation from pohradevi forest of washim district. IJARIE. Vol-3 issue-2 pp 4953- 4956.
- ✓ Ruchita Pangriya (2015). Study of aromatic and medicated plants in Utrakhand, India: With Focus on role in employment generation and supply chain management. Int. J. Soc. Sci. Manage. Vol-2, issue-2: 148-156.
- ✓ Sabitha Sakkir, Maher Kabshaw and Mohamed Mehairbi (2012). Medicinal plants diversity and their conservation status in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). Journal of Medicinal Plants Research Vol. 6(7), pp. 1304-1322.
- ✓ Sahoo A.K. and Anil K. G. (2012). Ethnobotany studies in Odisha (1942-2011) in pursuit of plant conservation. Ethnobotany Vol. 24. PP. 29-42
- ✓ Saito, I., Oya, Y. & Shimojo, H. (1986a). Novel RNA family structure of hepatitis B virus expressed in human cells, using helper-free adenovirus vector. Journal of Virology 58, 554-560.
- ✓ Saito, I., Oya, Y. & Shimojo. (1986b). Charomids: cosmid vectors for efficient cloning and mapping of large or small restriction fragments. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, USA 83, 8664-8668.
- ✓ Saleh H, Azizollah JK, Ahmadreza H, Raham A (2015). The Application of *Thymus vulgaris* in traditional and modern medicine: A Review. Global Journal of Pharmacology. 9 (3): 260-266.
- ✓ Sanchez-Lamar, A.; M. Fiore; E. Cundari; R. Ricordy; R. Cozzi y R. De Salvia (1999) *Phyllanthus orbicularis* aqueous extract: cytotoxic, genotoxic, and antimutagenic effects in the CHO cell line. Toxicol Appl Pharm 161: 231-39.
- ✓ Sandhya S B, Koteswars Rao J and SeetharamiReddi T V V(2011).Plant used in megico-religious beliefs by the tribes of Vishakhapatnam district AP. Ethnobotany, Vol. 23 PP 100-105.
- ✓ Sanjay R. Biradar & Bhagyashri D. Rachetti (2013a). Extraction of some secondary metabolites and thin layer chromatography from different parts of *Acacia farnesiana*

- L. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences (IOSR-JPBS). Volume 7, Issue 5 (Sep. – Oct. 2013), PP 44-48.
- ✓ Sanjay R. Biradar, Bhagyashri D. Rachetti (2013). Extraction of some secondary metabolites & thin layer chromatography from different parts of *Centella asiatica* L. (URB). American Journal of Life Sciences, 1(6): 243-247
 - ✓ Sanjay R. Biradar, Bhagyashri D. Rachetti (2013b). Extraction of some secondary metabolites & thin layer chromatography from different parts of *Centella asiatica* L. (URB). American Journal of Life Sciences. 1(6): 243-247.
 - ✓ Sanjay, R.B., Bhagyashri, D. R. (2013). Extraction of some secondary metabolites & thin layer chromatography from different parts of *Centella asiatica* L. (URB). American J. Life Sci. 1(6), 243-247.
 - ✓ Sanjeet Kumar, K. Jyotirmayee, Monalisa Sarangi (2013). Thin Layer Chromatography: A Tool of Biotechnology for Isolation of Bioactive Compounds from Medicinal Plants. Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res., 18(1), 126-132.
 - ✓ Santapu H., Henry AN. (1973). The Dictionary of the flowering plants in India New delhi. 79 ; 185.
 - ✓ Sarker, S.D. & Nahar, L. (2007). Chemistry for Pharmacy Students General, Organic and Natural Product Chemistry. England: John Wiley and Sons. pp 283-359.
 - ✓ Sati SP, Chaukiyalo DC (2001). 2D NMR Structure elucidation of a new Coumarin glycoside from *Xeromphis spinosa*. Srinagar (Garbwal). Vol-3; 174.
 - ✓ Saurabh Rajvaidhya, Gajendra Kamal Singh, Badri Prakash Nagori and Shashi Alok (2014). Extraction, Isolation and Chemical Structure Elucidation Of Daidzein From Bark Of Acacia Arabica (Lam.) Willd Of Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India.. 5(5): 2014-2021.
 - ✓ Scalbert A (1991). Antimicrobial properties of tannin. Phytochem. 30:3875-3883.
 - ✓ Schafer H, Wink M, (2009). Medicinally important secondary metabolites in recombinant microorganisms or plants: progress in alkaloid biosynthesis. Biotechnology Journal, 4(12): 1684- 1703.
 - ✓ Schippmann, U.; Leaman, D.J. and Cunningham, A.B. (2002). Impact of Cultivation and Gathering of medicinal plants on Biodiversity: Global Trends and Issues.

- In: Biodiversity and the Ecosystem Approach in Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries. FAO, 1-21.
- ✓ Schmelzer GH, Omino EA (2003). Plant Resources of Tropical Africa. Proceedings of the First PROTA International Workshop, 23-25 September, 2002, Nairobi, Kenya. PROTA Foundation, Wageningen, the Netherlands, p. 360.
 - ✓ Schulz, V., Hänsel, R. & Tyler, V.E. (2001) Rational Phytotherapy. A Physician's Guide to Herbal Medicine, 4th Ed., Berlin, Springer-Verlag.
 - ✓ Seetharam Y.N. and Kotresha Sekharappa Katrahalli (1998) Foliar venation of some species of *Bauhinia* L. and *Hardwickia binata* roxb. (Caesalpinioideae). Phytomorphology, 48(1), pp. 51-59.
 - ✓ Selvakumar Sivagnanam, and Anoop Prakash Chandra (2016). Preliminary phytochemical Analysis of *Amarathus viridis*. Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences. 7(1) PP 1-7.
 - ✓ Selvamani S and Balamurugan S (2015). Phytochemical Screening and GC-MS Analysis of Acetone Leaf Extract of *Acalypha indica* (Linn.). International Journal of Research Studies in Biosciences (IJRSB) Volume 3, Issue 5, May 2015, PP 229-232.
 - ✓ Senthamil Selvan P and Velavan S (2015), Analysis of bioactive compounds in methanol extract of *Cissus vitiginea* leaf using GC-MS technique, Rasayan J. Chem., 8(4), , 443-447.
 - ✓ Senthilkumar, P.K., Reetha, D. (2011). Isolation and identification of antibacterial compound from the leaves of *Cassia auriculata*: European Review for Medical and Pharmacological Sciences, Volume 15, Issue 9, Pages 1034-1038. PMID: 22013726.
 - ✓ Serafini, M., A. Ghiselli and A. Ferro-Luzzi. (1994). Red wine, tea and anti-oxidants. Lancet 344:626.
 - ✓ Sermakkani M. and Thangapandian V (2012). GC-MS analysis of *Cassia italica* leaf methanol extract. Asian J Pharm Cli Res., ; 5(2): 90- 94.
 - ✓ Shafaghat, A. (2011). Antioxidant, antimicrobial activities and fatty acid components of flower, Leaf, Stem and seed of *Hypericum scabrum*. Nat. Prod. Commun. 6, 1739–1742.

- ✓ Shankar K, Liao LP (2004) Traditional systems of medicine. *Phys Med Rehabil Clin N Am* 15: 725-747.
- ✓ Sharanabasappa G K, Santosh M K, Shaila D, Seetharam Y N And Sanjeevarao I S. (2007). Phytochemical Studies On *Bauhinia racemosa* Lam. *Bauhinia purpurea* Linn. And *Hardwickia binata* Roxb. *E-Journal of Chemistry* Vol. 4, No.1, Pp 21-31.
- ✓ Sharanabasappa G, Mallikharjuna PB, Rajanna LN and Seetharam YN (2010). Antibacterial and analgesic activities of *Bauhinia racemosa* Lam and *Hardwickia binata* Leaf extracts. *Pharmacologyonline* 2: 557-560.
- ✓ Sharma PC, Yelne MB, DenisJJ (2000). Data base on Medicinal plants used in Ayurveda.; Vol-2 ;380-3
- ✓ Sharma R M., (2000), check list of Indian grass gall midges (*Diptera: cecidoomyiidae*) with their host grass (poaceae) index. *Zoo's print journal*. Vol 15, issue 7 pp-297-299
- ✓ Sheetal Verma and S.P. Singh (2008). Current and future status of herbal medicines. *Veterinary World* Vol.1(11): 347-350
- ✓ Shiddamallayya N., Yasmeen A., Gopakumar K (2010). Hundred common forest medicinal plants of Karnataka in primary healthcare. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*. 9(1):90–95
- ✓ Simonsen, H. T. (2000). Nordskjold, J. B.; Smitt, U. W.; Nyman, U.; Palpu, P.; Joshi, P.; Varughese, G. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology.*, 74, 195-204. 13.
- ✓ Singhal M. And Sharma S. (2014) Medicinal Plants And Old Source Of New Drugs For Diabetes, *Bioinfo Drug Targets*. Volume 2, Issue 1, Pp-11-13.
- ✓ Singhal S, N singhal, S Agarwal (2009). *Pharmaceutical analysis-II, Thin Layer Chromatography*, Pragati Prakashan, first edition 98-111.
- ✓ Si-Yuan Pan, Gerhard Litscher, Si-Hua Gao, Shu-Feng Zhou, Zhi-Ling Yu, Hou-Qi Chen, Shuo-Feng Zhang, Min-Ke Tang, Jian-Ning Sun, and Kam-Ming Ko (2014). Historical Perspective of Traditional Indigenous Medical Practices: The Current Renaissance and Conservation of Herbal Resources. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. Article ID 525340, 20 pages.

- ✓ Soetan KO (2008). Pharmacological and other beneficial effects of Antinutritional factors in Plants- A Review. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 7(25): 4713-4721.
- ✓ Sofowora A (1993). *Medicinal Plants and Traditional Medicine in Africa*. Spectrum Books Ltd., Ibadan, Nigeria, pp. 191-289.
- ✓ Somchit, M.N., Reezal, I., Elysha, N.I. and Mutalib, A.R., (2003). In vitro antimicrobial activity of ethanol and water extracts of *Cassia alata*. *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 84: 1-4. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741\(02\)00146-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741(02)00146-0).
- ✓ Souti Khatua, Akhil Pandey and Surjyo Jyoti Biswas. (2016), Phytochemical evaluation and antimicrobial properties of *Trichosanthes dioica* root extract. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*; 5(5): 410-413).
- ✓ Stray F (1998). *The natural guide to medicinal herbs and plants*. Tiger Books International, London. pp 12-16.
- ✓ Strohl WR (2000). The role of natural products in modern drug discovery. *Drug Discov Today* 5:39–41.
- ✓ Subrat N. (2002). Ayurvedic and herbal products industry: an overview. Paper at workshop on Wise Practices and Experiential Learning in the Conservation and Management of Himalayan Medicinal Plants, Kathmandu, Nepal, 15-20,
- ✓ Sudahnshu Kumar and Anil K. Goel (2008). A purview of odoriferous plants found around Itechgarh hills in Crmanjhi black of Jharkhand. *Ethnobotany*, Vol. 20 PP 135-137.
- ✓ Sudhir Sharma, Neelima Rathi , Barkha Kamal , Dipika Pundir , Baljinder Kaur and Sarita Arya (2010). Conservation of biodiversity of highly important medicinal plants of India through tissue culture technology- a review. *Agric. Biol. J. N. Am.* (5): 827-833.
- ✓ Sumner J (2000). *The natural history of medicinal plants*. Timber Press, Portland, USA.
- ✓ Sunayana N, Prakash HS. (2012) – Fungal endophytes of *Boswellia Serrata* Roxb. (Burseraceae), a medicinal tree species. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences* 1(6), 1–5.

- ✓ Sunayana, N. and Prakash, H. S. (2012). Fungal Endophytes of *Boswellia Serrata* Roxb. (Burseraceae), a Medicinal Tree Species. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences (IOSRJPBS). Volume 1, Issue 6, PP 01-05.
- ✓ Suresh Chand and Ajay Kumar Singh (2001). Direct somatic embryogenesis from zygotic embryos of a timber-yielding leguminous tree, *Hardwickia binata* Roxb. Current Science, Vol. 80, NO. 7.
- ✓ Szczepanik, M., Zawitowska, B. and Szumny, A. (2012) Insecticidal Activities of *Thymus vulgaris* Essential Oil and Its Components (Thymol and Carvacrol) against Larvae of Lesser Mealworm, *Alphitobius diaperinus* Panzer (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). Allelopathy Journal, 30, 129-142.
- ✓ Tabuti J.R.S., Lye K.A. and Dhillion S.S. (2003). Traditional herbal drugs of Bulamogi, Uganda: plants, use and administration. Journal of Ethnopharmacology. 88, PP- 19–44.
- ✓ Tadesse W, Desalegn G, Alia R. (2007). Natural gum and resin bearing species of Ethiopia and their potential applications. Investigación Agraria – Sistemas y Recursos Forestales. 16:211–221.
- ✓ Tarapore VT, Shelav AR, Ankalagi RF, Daulatabad CD (1982). Components of fatty acid of *Randia Spionosa* poir synonym *Randia Dumetorum*. J Shivaji University (Sci). – 83: Vol- 21; 13 – 4.
- ✓ Taylor, L. (2000) Plant Based Drugs and Medicines. Raintree Nutrition Inc., Carson City, NV.
- ✓ Thenmozhi M and Rajeshwarisivaraj (2010). Phytochemical and antimicrobial evaluation of *Eclipta alba*. International journal of Advances in Pharmaceutical Research. Vol. 2 Issue. 6 PP-246 – 251.
- ✓ Thermo Nicolet Corporation (2001): Introduction to Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometry', by thermo Nicolet corporation.
- ✓ Tilburt JC, Kaptchuk TJ (2008) Herbal medicine research and global health: an ethical analysis. Bull World Health Organ 86: 594-599.

- ✓ Trease GE, Evans WC (1978). Pharmacology 11th Ed. Bailliere Tindall Ltd, London. pp 60-75.
- ✓ Trease, G.E. and Evans, W.C. (1989): Pharmacognosy. 13th (ed). ELBS/Bailliere Tindall, London. Pp. 345-6, 535-6, 772-3.
- ✓ Tribhubana Pandaa and Rabindra N Padhy (2008). Ethnomedicinal plants used by tribes of Kalahandi district, Orissa. Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge. Vol. 7(2), April 2008, pp. 242-249.
- ✓ Trivedi P C. (2010). Ethnobotany, Aaviskar Publication, Distributers Jaipur.
- ✓ Troup, R. S. (1998), The Silviculture of Indian Trees: Leguminosae (Caesalpinieae) to Verbenaceae, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1998, vol. 2, pp. 340–362.
- ✓ Tyler VE, Brady LR, Robers JE (1998). Pharmacognosy, K.M.Vargheese Company; Mumbai. 9th ed: 1988.
- ✓ UNESCO (1996). Culture and Health, Orientation Texts – World Decade for Cultural Development 1988 – 1997, Document CLT/DEC/PRO – 1996, Paris, France, pgs. 129.
- ✓ UNESCO (1998). FIT/504-RAF-48 Terminal Report: Promotion of Ethnobotany and the Sustainable Use of Plant Resources in Africa, pgs. 60, Paris, 1998.
- ✓ Urquiaga I and Leighton F. (2000). Plant polyphenol antioxidants and oxidative stress. Biological Research 33: 55–64.
- ✓ Vaishali Rai M, Vinitha Ramanath Pai, Pratapchandra Kedilaya H, Smitha Hegde (2013). Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of Members of Lamiaceae Family: *Leucas linifolia*, *Coleus aromaticus* and *Pogestemon patchouli* int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res., 21(1) 22, 131-137.
- ✓ Van Etten H, Temporini E, Wasmann C, (2001). Phytoalexin (and phytoanticipin) tolerance as a virulence trait: why is it not required by all pathogens? Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology, 59: 83-93.
- ✓ Van Wyk, B.-E., Van Oudtshoorn, B., Gericke, N., (1997). Medicinal Plants of South Africa, 2nd Improved Impression (2000). Briza Publications, Pretoria.

- ✓ Venkata, R.B., Samuel, L.A., Pardha, S.M., Narashimha, R.B., Krishna, N.V., Sudhakar, M., Radhakrishnan, T.M., (2012). Antibacterial, antioxidant activity and GC–MS analysis of *Eupatorium odoratum*. *Asian J. Pharm. Clin. Res.* 5 (2), 99–106.
- ✓ Verma, S.; Singh, S. P. (2008). Current and future status of herbal medicines. *Veterinary World.* 1, 347-350. 12.
- ✓ Verpoorte, R., Memelink, J. (2002). Engineering secondary metabolite production in plants. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* 13: 181–187.
- ✓ Verpoorte, R., van der Heijden, R., Hoge, J.H.C., ten Hoopen, H.J.G. (1994). Plant cell biotechnology for the production of secondary metabolites. *Pure and Applied Chemistry* 66: 2307–2310.
- ✓ Vijisaral Elezabeth D. and Arumugam S. (2014). GC-MS analysis of bioactive constituents of *Indigofera suffruticosa* leaves. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 6(8):294-300
- ✓ Vishwakarma, A.P., Vishwe, A., Sahu, P. and Chaurasiya, A. (2013) Magical Remedies of *Terminalia arjuna* (ROXB.). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Archive*, 2, 189-201.
- ✓ Vitor CE, Figueiredo CP, Hara DB, Bento AF, Mazzuco TL, Calixto JB (2009.) Therapeutic action and underlying mechanisms of a combination of two pentacyclic triterpenes, alpha- and beta-amyrin, in a mouse model of colitis. *Br J Pharmacol.* 157: 1034-1044. 10.1111/j.1476-5381.2009.00271.x.
- ✓ Vohora SB, Khan MS, Afaq SH (1998). Antifertility studies on Unani herbs: anti-ovulatory and anti-implantation effects of Mainphal. *Indian Journal of Pharmacy.* Vol-36: 164-5.
- ✓ Wang, Y., Chen, W., Wu, Z., Xi, Z., Chen, W., Zhao, G., Li, X. & Sun, L. (2011). Chemical constituents from *Salacia amplifolia*, *Biochemical Systematics and Ecology*, 39: 205-208. ISSN: 0305-1978.
- ✓ Wani M C, Taylor H L, Wall M E, Coggon P, Mcphail A T. (1971). Plant antitumor agents. VI. The isolation and structure of Taxol, a novel antileukemic and antitumour agents from *Taxus brevifolia*. *J Am Chem Soc*, 93: 2325-2327.

- ✓ Warriar PK, Ramankutty C, Nair RV (2000). Indian Medicinal Plant- A Compendium of 500 Species. Orient Longman: Vol-III ;32-6.
- ✓ WHO (2002). WHO Traditional Medicine Strategy 2002-2005, World Health Organization Bulletin.
- ✓ William Charles Evans (1996). Trease and Evans Pharmacognosy, W.B.Saunders Company; London. 14th ed.
- ✓ Xiao, P. (1988) A Pictorial Encyclopaedia of Chinese Medicine. v1-10. Commercial Press, Hong Kong, 88-90.
- ✓ Yang, L. H. (2006). Interactions between a detrital resource pulse and a detritivore community. *Oecologia* 147:522–532.
- ✓ Yik Sin Chan, Bee Ling Chuah, Wei Quan Chan, Ri Jin Cheng, Yan Hang Oon, Kong Soo Khoo, Nam Weng Sit (2014). Valuation of Medicinal Plants, *Catunaregam spinosa*, *Houttuynia cordata*, and *Rhapis excelsa* from Malaysia for Antibacterial, Antifungal and Antiviral Properties. *International Journal of Pharmacological and Pharmaceutical Sciences* Vol:1, No:11,
- ✓ Yusuf, A. Z., Zakir, A., Shemau, Z., Abdullahi, M. and Halima, S. A. (2014)., Phytochemical analysis of the methanol leaves extract of *Paullinia pinnata* linn, *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*, Vol. 6(2), pp. 10-16, DOI: 10.5897/JPP2013.0299.
- ✓ Zahra Lorigooini, Farzad Kobarfard, Seyed Abdolmajid Ayatollahi (2014). Anti-platelet aggregation assay and chemical composition of essential oil from *Allium atroviolaceum* Boiss growing in Iran. *International Journal of Biosciences*. Vol. 5, No. 2, p. 151-156
- ✓ Zhang, H.W., Y.C. Song and R.X. Tan. (2006). Biology and chemistry of endophytes. *Nat. Pro. Rep.*, 23: 753-771.

List of Publications

1. M. B. Patil, M. S. Shaikh and **P. A. Khan (2015)**. “Conservational Studies on *Chlorophytum Borivilianum* (SafedMusli) In Nandurbar District, Maharashtra. *American Research Thought*. ISSN: 2392-76x Vol. 1 (6). **IF: 2.0178**
2. M. B. Patil and **P. A. Khan (2015)**. “Ethnomedicinal Studies of *Acalypha Indica* L. (Euphorbiaceae)”. *Review of Research Journal*, Volume-4 (7). Pp 1-6 ISSN: 2249-894X (UGC Approved Journal Sr. No 48514.) **IF: 3.140**
3. M. B. Patil, **P. A. Khan** and M. Shaikh (2015). “Ethno Ecological Knowledge and Medicinal Flora from South-Western Satpuda, Maharashtra”. *Life Sciences Leaflets*. Vol. 63 2015. Pp 44-56. ISSN 2277-4297. **IF: 1.2210**
4. M. B. Patil and **P. A. Khan, (2016)**. Review: Techniques towards the Plant Phytochemical. *International Journal of Science Info (IJSI)*, Vol. I. Issue 3. PP-157-172
5. M. B. Patil and **P. A. Khan (2017)**. Ethnobotanical, phytochemical and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer (FTIR) studies of *Catunaregam spinosa* (Thunb.) Tirven. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. Vol. 10 Issue 2 PP 950-955 (UGC Approved Journal Sr. No 21822.)
6. M. B. Patil and **P. A. Khan (2017)**. “Primary Phytochemical Studies of *Catunaregam spinosa* (Thunb.) Tirven for Secondary Metabolites”. *Int J Pharm Bio Sci* 2017 Apr ; 8(2): (P) 320-323. SJIF 6.268 (UGC Approved Journal Sr. No 17357.) **IF: 6.268**
7. M. B. Patil and **P. A. Khan (2017)**. “Economical and Ethical Aspects in Medicinal Plant Research”. *RESEARCH REVIEW International Journal of Multidisciplinary*. Vol: 2, Issue:2 June-2017. (UGC Approved Journal Sr. No. 44945) **IF: 4.184**

List of Conferences Attend /Participate / participated:

1. Oral presentation at “**National Conference** on Advance in Bioscience and Environmental Science: Present and Future ABES- 2015”. Department of Life Sciences, BP Arts, SMA Science & KKC Commerce College, Chalisgaon Dist- Jalgaon. Date: 22nd – 23rd Sept **2015**.
2. Oral presentation : M. B. Patil and **P. A. Khan** (2016). “Economical and Ethnical Aspects in Medicinal Plant Research”. **International Conference** on “Impact of Globalization on cross culture and ethical issue in Arts and Media, Commerce and Management and Science & Technology” on 13th and 14th September 2016. Held at RNC Arts, JDB Com & NSC Sci College, Nashik Road- 422101- Nashik
3. Poster presentation on, “Ethnobotanical and phytochemical studies of *Catunaregum spinosa* (Thunb.)Tirven” At A One Day Multi Disciplinary **National Conference** on “Biodiversity & Environmental Impact, Second Prize for best presentation of paper 24th Dec 2016.

Achievements

Awarded Second Prize in Multidisciplinary **National Conference on BIODIVERSITY & ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT (NCBEI 2016)**, the Poster entitled “**Ethnomedicinal & Phytochemical Studies of *Catunaregum spinosa***”, held at Narmadabai Nago Chaudhri Arts, Commerce & Science College, Kusumba, tal. Dist Dhule (M.S.) Sponsored by **North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon**. on 24 December 2016.

**(Dr. Patil Madhukar B.)
Signature of the Guide**